

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

In collaboration with

 Qnostics

**Development of a multiplex control to support the
comparison and control of molecular assays used
for the detection of Carbapenemase-Producing
Enterobacterales.**

Heather Hurst

Submitted in fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Master of Research

University of the West of Scotland
School of Health and Life Sciences
In collaboration with Qnostics Ltd
2024-2025

Declaration by Candidate

I, Heather Hurst hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is my own work and has not been submitted in part or whole, for any other degrees at this, or any other University or Institute. Where other sources of information have been used, they have been acknowledged in the appropriate format.

Ethical Considerations

This project did not require ethical approval from the School of Health & Life Sciences.

Signed:

Date: 14 AUG 2025

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Abstract

Enterobacteriales that produce acquired carbapenemases are referred to as Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriales (CPE), which are a family of bacteria that have acquired resistance to carbapenem antibiotics. Increased colonisation of CPE within the gastrointestinal tract is a growing global public health threat. Rapid and accurate detection is vital to limit outbreaks, reduce transmission of resistant genes, lessen health care costs and ultimately decrease mortality and morbidity rates.

Developing CPE positive control (PC) materials will contribute significantly to the improvement in the analytical performance of molecular methodologies used for CPE detection and will permit laboratories to monitor their accuracy and effectiveness thus ensuring reliable and consistent results. The PC is intended to mimic positive patient samples, consisting of known concentrations of Carbapenem-resistance genes, allowing the evaluation of molecular detection methods from extraction phase through to amplification. Validation at every stage of the testing process can be identified and monitored and staff training can be provided through the PC material.

This project involved the development of molecular in-house quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assays for the five most prevalent carbapenemase enzymes (Klebsiella pneumoniae carbapenemase (KPC), New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase (NDM), Verona Integron-mediated metallo- β -lactamase (VIM), Imipenem-resistant Pseudomonas (IMP), and OXA-48-type carbapenem-hydrolysing class D β -lactamase (OXA-48)). A CPE multiplex control was then developed that is capable of detecting the five genes mentioned above and will contribute to aiding laboratories in their development and assessment of their molecular assay performance. The control was assessed using the qPCR assays and Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay and then characterised with digital PCR. The results obtained in this project illustrate that the positive control material developed is viable for use with in-house qPCR assays and Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay, with reliable performance in detecting the five carbapenemase genes. The public health threat posed by the spread of these organisms is an escalating global concern and so it is vital that steps must be taken to control and manage CPE detection allowing outbreaks and spread of Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) to be controlled. Therefore, the PC material will contribute to the development and accurate detection of CPE in a clinical setting.

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List of Abbreviations

ABI	Applied Biosystems
ABS	Absolute Quantification
<i>AmpC</i>	<i>AmpC cephalosporinases</i>
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
APCs	Artificial Positive Controls
AU	Arbitrary Units
BHQ1	Black Hole Quencher 1
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
CPE	Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales
Cq	Cycle quantification
CRE	Carbapenem-resistant <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>
Ct	Cycle threshold
dc/mL	digital copies per Millilitre
ddPCR	Droplet digital polymerase chain reaction
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EQA	External Quality Assessment
ESBLs	Extended-spectrum β -lactamases
FAM	Fluorescein amidites
GNB	Gram-negative bacteria
HEX	Hexachlorofluorescein
HGT	Horizontal gene transfer
IC	Internal Control
IHA	In House Assay
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IMP	Imipenem-resistant <i>Pseudomonas</i>
KPC	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> carbapenemase
LoD	Limit of detection
LoQ	Limit of quantitation
MBLs	Metallo- β -lactamases
MDR	Multidrug-resistant

mL	Millilitre
NC	Negative Control
NDM	New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase
NTC	No-template control
OXA-48	OXA-48-type carbapenem-hydrolysing class D β -lactamase
PBPs	Penicillin-binding proteins
PC	Positive Control
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PT	Proficiency testing
qPCR	Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction
QS	Quality Standard
R ²	Coefficient of determination
RSD	Relative Standard Deviation
SAV	Salmonid Alphavirus
SD	Standard Deviation
TE	Tris EDTA
T _m	Melting temperature
UKAS	United Kingdom Accreditation Service
VIC	VIC Phosphoramidite
VIM	Verona Integron-mediated metallo- β -lactamase
WG	Whole Gene
WHO	World Health Organization
μ L	Microlitre
μ M	Micromolar

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Carbapenemases

1.1.1 Background

Enterobacteriaceae, a family of Gram-negative bacteria (GNB) consists of Enterobacterales, bacteria including *Enterobacter* species, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* species. These organisms usually exist in the guts of animals and humans typically without causing harm; however, they are responsible for a variety of common infections in healthcare settings and within the community. Clinically, they are involved in a wide spectrum of infections which can include bloodstream, intra-abdominal and urinary tract infections. The burden of infections caused by these organisms is of particular concern to public health especially to vulnerable populations such as the immunocompromised and those with prolonged hospital stays (Inmaculada López Montesinos et al., 2024 Enterobacterales producing acquired carbapenemase are referred to as Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (CPEs) (Tilahun et al., 2021).

Carbapenems are β -lactam, broad-spectrum, antibiotic agents originally produced by some bacteria within the Enterobacteriaceae family According to Armstrong, Fenn and Hardie (2021), the first recorded Carbapenem, thienamycin, was discovered in 1976. However, due to its instability in aqueous solutions, further structural optimisation led to the development of a number of carbapenems that are used clinically. These antibiotics include meropenem and imipenem shown in Figure 1, as well as ertapenem and doripenem. These antibiotics work by interfering with bacteria cells walls, blocking transpeptidation which is a vital step in peptidoglycan crosslinking leading to cell lysis and death. They achieve this by binding with penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) resulting in the inactivation of intracellular autolytic inhibitor enzymes and promotes bacterial self-destruction.

As described by Lima et al., 2020 Carbapenems core structure consists of an unsaturated 4:5 fused ring system with a methylene substitution in place of sulphur which is a C2 substitute. This substitution contributes to the unique chemical properties of Carbapenems. Additionally, Carbapenems also contain a C2-C3 double bond, with a key structural feature being the (S)-configured hydroxyethyl side chain at C6 which aids with β -lactamase resistance, contributing to their broad-spectrum activity.

Figure 1 illustrates the chemical structure of several key Carbapenems, highlighting their shared core and variations in side chains that effect how they work and how they are processed.

Figure 1. Structure of Carbapenems

Adapted from Armstrong, Fenn and Hardie, 2021.

Carbapenems are considered the broadest spectrum agents of the β -lactam antibiotics and are typically reserved for the treatment of multidrug-resistant (MDR) Gram-Negative pathogens. They play a vital role in the treatment of severe infections proving to be resistant to other antibiotics (for e.g. penicillin and cephalosporin) and are often referred to as 'last-line agents or antibiotics of 'last resort'. Carbapenemases are versatile β -lactamase enzymes that hydrolyse β -lactam antibiotics. The genes encoding these enzymes are typically carried on plasmids which are capable of transferring between bacteria.

1.2 Classification

β -lactamases can be classified according to two main systems. The first is the Bush-Jacoby-Medeiros classification which is based on the functional characteristics of the enzymes, including isoelectric points, substrate profiles, and inhibitor characteristics (Bush and Jacoby, 2009). The second and most widely used, is the Ambler molecular classification scheme, which categorises β -lactamases bases on their primary structure, dividing them according to their amino acid sequences into four classes A, B, C and D (Sheu et al., 2019). Table 1 summarises the Ambler classification system, excluding Class C, as carbapenemases from this class are not the focus of this project. Instead, the emphasis was on 'the big 5' carbapenemases, which fall within Classes A, B and D.

Table 1. Classification and Characteristics of Major Carbapenemases in Enterobacteriaceae.

Adapted from Sheu et al., 2019.

Carbapenemase	KPC	MBLs (NDM, VIM, IMP)	OXA-48
Ambler Molecular Class	A	B	D
Substrate of hydrolysis	All β -lactams	All β -lactams except for aztreoam	Penicillins and carbapenems
Inhibited by classic β -lactamase inhibitors	Minimally	No	No
Inhibited by avibactam	Yes	No	Yes
Inhibited by vaborbactam	Yes	No	No
Inhibited by relebactam	Yes	No	No
Common species in Enterobacteriaceae	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Enterobacter</i> <i>spp.</i>	NDM: <i>K. pneumoniae</i> , <i>E. coli</i> VIM: <i>K. pneumoniae</i> IMP: <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>

The serine β -lactamases classes A and D which include KPC and OXA-48 use a hydrolytic mechanism involving a nucleophilic serine residue. Class B serine β -lactamases include the metallo- β -lactamases (MBLs) VIM, NDM and IMP. These enzymes can hydrolyse β -lactams using a water molecule activated by one or more zinc ions (Mora-Ochomogo and Lohans, 2021). Class C serine β -lactamases are known as the AmpC β -lactamases according to the Ambler scheme. They can be found on various Enterobacteriaceae, AmpC genes that are encoded chromosomally to Enterobacteriaceae species (Jacoby, 2009).

1.3 Enzymes of Interest: β -lactamases

1.3.1 KPC (*Klebsiella pneumoniae* carbapenemase)

In 1996 KPC was first identified in the USA in *K. pneumoniae* isolates (Yigit *et al.*, 2001). The production of KPC enzymes has led to issues in infection control as they are a key mechanism of resistance. There are 24 different coding genes (bla_{KPC}) that have been identified. Infections caused by organisms producing KPCs have high mortality and morbidity rates, and there are limited treatment options (Porreca, Sullivan and Gallagher, 2018). KPC is considered endemic in several countries including China, Greece, Italy and the USA. This rapid spread across the world is largely due to clonal expansion of strains of *K. pneumoniae*. KPC have been reported in *K. pneumoniae*, *Enterobacterales* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Logan and Weinstein 2017).

1.3.2 IMP (*Imipenem-Resistant Pseudomonas*)

Imipenem-resistant *Pseudomonas* (IMP-1) was identified in Japan in 1991 (Watanabe, *et al.*, 1991). IMP are plasmid-encoding carbapenemases and is a family in Class B that needs zinc for β -lactam hydrolysis and primarily confers resistance against imipenem and meropenem. There are around 88 variants which are most prevalent in Asia, specifically China (Cai *et al.*, 2019). IMP have been reported in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and some variants reported in *Serratia marcescens* and *Enterobacterales* (Osano E, *et al.*, 1994).

1.3.3 VIM (*Verona Integron-encoded Metallo- β -lactamases*)

VIM was first identified in Verona, Italy in 1997 (Lauretti *et al.*, 1999). They are encoded by genes (bla_{VIM}) and are the most prevalent types of MBL's. There are more than 40 variants of VIM with VIM-1 and VIM-2 being the most common. They have been reported in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *E. coli* (Lawrence *et al.* 2024). They have been reported in several countries including the USA, European and South American countries (Reyes *et al.*, 2023).

1.3.4 NDM (*New Delhi Metallo- β -lactamases*)

New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase (NDM) is an enzyme that confers resistance to carbapenem antibiotics, contributing significantly to the global challenges of antimicrobial resistance. NDM can spread rapidly through horizontal gene transfer (HGT). HGT is the non-reproductive exchange of genetic information between organisms, facilitating the spread of resistant genes. NDM was first isolated from a

Swedish patient of Indian descent hospitalised in New Delhi, India in 2008 (Yong et al., 2009). Since its discovery, NDM has been predominantly reported in *K. pneumoniae*, and *E. coli*. The enzyme is now considered endemic in India where widespread and often unregulated use of antibiotics combined with limited antibiotic surveillance has led to outbreaks and resistance to many antibiotics. NDM has demonstrated global distribution with increased occurrences reported in several countries. Asia serves as the primary reservoir for NDM-1, particularly China and India accounting for 58.15%. Several other countries have had widespread detection documented including the UK, USA, Japan and Egypt, reflecting the global spread of this enzyme (Khan, Maryam and Zarilli, 2017).

1.3.5 OXA (OXA-48-type carbapenem-hydrolysing class D β -lactamase)

Oxacillinase (OXA)-48 was isolated in Turkey from *K. pneumoniae* in 2004 (Poirel et al., 2003). The most prevalent CPE in Europe, the Middle East and Northern Africa are OXA-48 and OXA-48 like enzymes (Boyd et al., 2022). OXA-48 enzymes hydrolyse penicillins and carbapenems. They have been generally reported in *A. baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and members of *Enterobacteriaceae* (*E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) (Pitout et al 2019).

The global distribution and occurrence of the five enzymes discussed is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Occurrence and Geographic Distribution of CPE Worldwide by Resistance Mechanism.

Based on a literature review from 2015 (Friedman et al., 2017).

1.4 State of the market- Need for Molecular Controls and Proficiency Testing

Accurate detection of CPE is vital in minimising transmissions and allowing sufficient infection control procedures to be implemented within hospital settings. To guarantee reliable laboratory results, appropriate management and validation of the detection methods are required.

Molecular controls are essential for evaluating the performance of an assay workflow, ensuring that accurate detection has occurred with reliable results. When a molecular test is unable to accurately detect or quantify controls the results cannot be relied upon. A variety of controls can be used in molecular diagnostics to assess the assay at different stages of the assay workflow. These include the following:

- **Positive Controls (PCs):** These confirm that detection of specific target analyte is possible. PCs should contain clinically relevant levels of the analyte of interest within an appropriate matrix which ensures that the assays sensitivity is sufficient for detection and quantification. Samples that mimic positive clinical material allow true identification and quantification of clinical samples.
- **Negative controls (NCs):** Set out to represent a 'true negative' result and should not be detectable, as they do not contain target analyte. They controls can be used at multiple stages of a workflow, for example during Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) extraction, amplification and at the analytical stage, monitoring false positive results and contamination.
- **Internal controls (ICs):** Verify that distinct stages of the testing workflow are valid. Exogenous internal controls can be added directly into the sample leading to monitoring of a specific stage of the process for example spiking sample material with a known internal control during extraction stage allows for the quality of the extraction to be assured.
- **Human reference materials/cell lines:** These can be used as appropriate positive controls but can be difficult to source and may pose a considerable risk of infection to sample handlers. An alternative is the use of synthetic controls, such as plasmid constructs with known concentrations that can simulate targets closely and offer a more accessible substitute. The use of synthetic controls pose a higher risk of contamination in laboratories.

1.5 Resistance

The emergence of pathogens resistant to carbapenems represents a growing global public health concern. Infections caused by these organisms are linked with high morbidity and mortality (Paudel et al., 2024). Major outbreaks involving CPEs and Carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* (CRE) pose a significant threat due to increased levels of antimicrobial resistance. Given that Carbapenems are often considered as last resort antibiotics, used to treat severe bacterial infections, it is vital to limit their spread.

One key recommendation highlighted in the UK Health and Security Agency (UKHSA, 2022) Framework set out to contain CPE, is for diagnostic laboratories to implement and use molecular or immunochromatographic assays to assist culture-based testing to detect key carbapenems. Along with measures such as prompt detection and management of outbreaks, effective surveillance systems and infection control procedures, the spread of CPE and CRE can be minimised and managed effectively.

Hospital-acquired infection rates have been rapidly increasing resulting in expanding morbidity and mortality rates. There are around 2.6 million new cases of these infections reported in Europe each year, with antimicrobial resistant microorganisms causing over 400,000 of them (Friedrich 2019). Annual CRE-reported cases in the UK have increased from three cases in 2003 to 1,893 cases in 2015 (Aldali et al., 2023). So, the emergence of CRE is considered an increasing global health concern with restricted treatment options, particularly in severe infections where carbapenems are used as the last resort antibiotic. This highlights a vital need for the rapid detection and identification of CRE and the development of new antibiotics and therapeutic treatment methods to limit outbreaks.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified antibacterial resistance as one of the pressing global health threats (WHO, 2024). The 2024 WHO Bacterial Priority Pathogens List (BPPL) highlights bacterial pathogens that are important to public health as they pose a threat due to their resistance to antibiotics. This list categorises pathogens into three propriety groups: critical, high ad medium. Contained in the critical group are Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. This list presented by the WHO contributes to guiding antimicrobial resistance control measures and indicates the significant role CRE plays in contributing to public health threat.

Supporting this, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) Risk Assessment Report (February 2025) provides significant insight into the risks associated with infections caused by these organisms. The urgent need for rapid and early detection is highlighted particularly due to notable increases in incidences of carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* associated bloodstream infections along with detection of *E.coli* harbouring resistant genes, the healthcare related spread of CRE and increase in detection of emerging species has collectively impacted the risks to public health. Aiesh et al., in 2023 further emphasise severity of the issue, reporting that 61.9% of patients screened in a hospital setting carried carbapenem-resistant *K.pneumoniae* and 38.1% harboured carbapenem-resistant *E.coli*.

To address these challenges, the report recommends strengthening laboratory capacity to detect these organisms which is pivotal for implementing preventative measures promptly. In this context, the development and introduction of appropriate molecular positive control materials, as explored in this project, offers a valuable tool for enhancing diagnostic accuracy and supporting infection control efforts.

1.6 Global Impact

CRE have become increasingly prevalent across the globe. Figure 3 below, shows the rapid increase in numbers of CRE (*K. pneumoniae*) across five countries in Europe (Friedman et al 2017).

Figure 3. Geographical Spread of Carbapenem-Resistant *K. pneumoniae* in Europe. Friedman et al., 2017.

In Greece, carbapenem resistance rates in hospital wards rose sharply from under 1% in 2001 to 30% by 2008. These rates reached 60% within intensive care units and by 2014, 62.3% of *K. pneumoniae* isolates being identified as resistant to carbapenems. In the United States, reports of KPC strains increased rapidly with detection rates doubling in 2006 compared to the previous year. An increase in CRE incidences was reported with around 3 cases per 100,00 people, with 47.3% of CRE isolates identified as CPE containing KPC. By 2016, 48 U.S. states had reported the presence of KPC-producing bacteria (Logan and Weinstein 2017).

A recent report by Aldali et al., 2023 investigated the prevalence of CRE acquired in hospital settings in the UK between 2009 and 2021, as shown by Figure 4 below. The study analysed data from across 63 hospitals and highlighted that 2,053 and 1,083 carbapenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae* (CRKP) and carbapenem-resistant *Escherichia*

coli (CREC) isolates were identified, respectively. This is particularly significant as three of the most prevalent carbapenemases KPC, NDM and OXA-like, are commonly associated with these bacterial species. The report explained that across 11 different studies included in the analysis, 2,043 KPC, 687 OXA-like and 26 NDM carbapenems were identified. This total of 2,756 carbapenemase-producing isolates reported highlight the escalating burden of CRE in UK healthcare organisations, further emphasising the requirement of advancements in infection control and detection measures implemented.

Figure 4. Reported Cases of Carbapenem Resistant K.pneumoniae (CRKP) and E.coli (CRE. coli) in the UK Between 2009 and 2020. The Y axis represents the number of reported isolates, while the X axis lists the corresponding studies from which that data has been compiled. Data was sourced from multiple publications. This figure is adapted from Aldali et al., 2023.

1.7 Mechanisms of Carbapenem Resistance

Carbapenemase production can inactivate carbapenems. β -lactamase genes carried on mobile genetic elements are a significant mechanism for the rapid spread of antibiotic-resistant GNB worldwide. The enzymes inactivate β -lactam antibiotics leading to the antibiotics being unable to target PBP's. They are the most common mechanism of resistance due to being encoded on plasmids and easily transferred via horizontal gene transfer (Mora-Ochomogo and Lohans, 2021). Extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) and AmpC cephalosporinases (AmpC) together with mutations of porins can confer resistance (Logan and Weinstein 2017). Porin modifications result in bacterial cell walls having fewer entry points (porins) for carbapenem action. Efflux pump upregulation can remove the antibiotics from the cells preventing their function (Vergalli et al., 2019).

1.8 Detection of CPE and Platforms Used for Diagnosis

The rapid spread of CPE poses a significant threat to public health in the UK and worldwide, outbreaks can be difficult to contain and costly to control. It is essential that diagnostic laboratories have a fast and reliable detection system in place to identify CPE to limit their spread and introduce accurate treatment and isolation measures. There are many different methods used for the detection of CPE. Each method has its own limitations and performance can vary.

1.8.1 Phenotypic Detection Methods

Culture based tests have long been considered the foundation of microbiological diagnostics. However, these detection methods are time consuming, taking on average 24–48 hours to determine a positive result. Even after initial detection further confirmation testing is often still required. In the event of outbreaks or high-risk cases the time to transport samples from different laboratories could have a significant impact diagnosis and treatment interventions.

The Carbapenem Inactivated Method (CIM) and its modified zinc supplemented CIM (zCIM) is a cost effective and simple phenotypic detection method. However, as reported by Baeza *et al.* (2019) the method exhibits limitations. The method can take a long time to produce viable results due to an overnight culture being required, which can delay the turnaround of results and limit its effectiveness in providing rapid

detection of CPE. The data also indicated high occurrence of both false negative and false positive reports, indicating issues with assay performance. Zhang et al., 2021 further evaluated the performance of CIM based platforms, reporting a sensitivity of 97.4% and specificity of 97.7%. However, the method demonstrated reduced efficacy in accurately classifying IMP and OXA-48-like enzymes. Although CIM-based platforms are affordable and accessible they lack the resolution required for precise classification of CPE genes.

1.8.2 Immunochromatographic Tests

These tests are rapid and easy to interpret and can be employed to detect the most prevalent carbapenemases, with results being detectable in under 30 minutes. A study conducted by Baeza *et al.*, 2019 assessed the tests performance with the following results: RESIST-4 O.K.N.V. (Coris BioConcept, Gembloux, Belgium) produced a sensitivity of 84.2% and specificity of 100%, with the assay being able to detect four of the major carbapenemases. The CARBA-5 platform was able to accurately detect the five most prevalent carbapenemases and has a Sensitivity of 88.2% and specificity of 100%. However, despite the rapid turnaround of results, then study highlighted that a number of false negative results occurred. This could significantly impact the transmission of resistant genes and negatively affect intervention and treatment options.

1.8.3 Colorimetric Test β -CARBA(Bio-Rad)

Baeza *et al.*, 2019 demonstrated that the β -CARBA (Bio-Rad) colorimetric test is a highly specific (100%), rapid and cost-effective detection method capable of detecting all IMP variants as well as rare OXA-58 carbapenemase variant. The test operates by visually detecting colour change results from the hydrolysis of a chromogenic substrate, which indicates the presence of carbapenemase activity. Despite the strengths of this detection method, the test reported false negatives results and s exhibited a low sensitivity of 73.7%.

1.8.4 Molecular Techniques

1.8.4.1 Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

PCR is a well-established molecular methodology widely used for detecting genetic markers in bacteria, including CPE. It is recognised for its high specificity and sensitivity

making it a reliable platform for the detection of resistance genes. The PCR process involves nucleic acid amplification, whereby double-stranded DNA are denatured at high temperatures, typically above 90°C, followed by the annealing of oligos and extension by DNA polymerase to synthesize a copy of single stranded DNA. This process allows the exponential amplification of target DNA.

Rapid turnaround in diagnostic testing can significantly reduce the time and resources required for infection control. Early detection enables timely implementation of containment measures, which are essential in limiting the spread of CPE. Faster diagnostic measures can therefore have a substantial impact on public health. PCR remains the gold standard for carbapenemase detection due to its high sensitivity and specificity. However, the method can rely on skilled staff and access to expensive laboratory equipment, which may limit its feasibility in settings with limited resources. .

One of the restrictions of PCR is that it relies on the detection of targeted genes and so new and emerging enzyme variants may not be detected (Baeza et al., 2019) and so should be used alongside culture-based methods. The major enzymes i.e. 'the big 5' can be detected quickly leading to faster treatment and management of potential outbreaks. Results can be obtained directly from patient stool or rectal swabs with no need for long culture methods (Solgi et al., 2024).

1.8.4.2 Microarray Technology

While PCR is a well-established and sensitive method used for the detection of CPE, it is limited due to constraints in primer design and fluorescence channel availability. In contrast, multiplex platforms and microarray-based technologies can offer broader detection capabilities. These can have benefits over PCR as they can include high numbers of targets, microarrays typically containing hundreds of probes making them a significant tool in profiling and characterising carbapenemase resistance (Paudel et al., 2024).

Commercial systems such as Verigene, BioFire FilmArray, and Check-Points provide multiplexed detection of key resistant genes. Additionally, the hyperplex SuperBug ID (eazyplex) can detect a wide number of carbapenemase genes including KPC, NDM, IMP, VIM, GIM, OXA-48, OXA-162, OXA-181, and OXA-204. As reported by Lutgring and Limbago, 2016. These platforms can enhance diagnostic throughput and are advantageous for rapid detection in clinical settings.

1.8.4.3 Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R

This is a PCR-based method of detecting the presence of KPC, NDM, VIM, IMP, and OXA-48 target sequences, widely used in public health care settings to screen for CPE. It is easy to use, has high reproducibility and is able to differentiate 5 of the most common carbapenemases. The study underscored the Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay can be relied upon for the accurate detection of CPE. Baeza et al., 2019 showed the platform to have a sensitivity value of 88.2% and specificity of 100%. However, this is an expensive detection platform as proprietary equipment is required.

1.8.4.4 AusDiagnostics MT CRE EU Assay

This method is a nested multiplex PCR detection platform with results gathered less than 4 hours after bacterial culture. A study conducted by Meunier, Woodford and Hopkins, 2018, evaluated the AusDiagnostics MT CRE EU assay (AusDiagnostics, Chesham, UK). The findings showed that the assay was able to identify 97.5% of the five carbapenemase genes assessed and detect their variants. The study showed that the assay performed well with a recorded sensitivity rate of 95.5% and specificity of 99.8%.

To summarise, a wide variety of carbapenemase detection methods are available, each with distinct advantages and limitations. The literature reviewed indicates that there is no single platform that is universally optimal across all clinical and laboratory settings. However, a combinatory approach, whereby multiple diagnostic methods are integrated which may offer an enhanced detection strategy and thereby informing more effective treatment and control strategies.

Considerations must be given when selecting an appropriate platform, namely test costs, if additional specialised equipment is required, how easy the method is to use, time to access results, how easy results are to interpret and overall diagnostic accuracy and reliability. Focus on five of the most prevalent genes, the 'big five,' would be a basic requirement when selecting a platform, however this may limit the detection of rare and emerging genes. This focus may inadvertently limit the detection of emerging and less frequent resistant genes causing misclassification, inaccurate detection and thereby resulting in inadequate interventions. Therefore, careful evaluation of the clinical context, laboratory capacity and surveillance requirements are vital when selecting a detection platform.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of this project is to develop a molecular reference control for Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriales (CPE). The control will be designed to be primarily compatible with Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay but also other polymerase chain reaction(PCR) molecular technologies which are widely used in public health settings to screen for CPE. The control provides an efficient and cost-effective method to validate assay performance and workflows detecting carbapenem-resistance.

- The first step of the project will be to perform a review of External Quality Assessment (EQA) data and literature to investigate the most prevalent CPE target sequences.
- In-house qualitative PCR assays will be developed for the targets (Chapter 2), and droplet digital PCR testing performed to produce quantitative assays. (Chapter 3).
- Simplex and multiplex controls will be developed and assessed as part of the study here based on literature to ensure they are at a clinically relevant level (Chapter 4).
- The proposed control formulation will be evaluated with available in-house and commercial assays (Chapter 4).

The project hypothesizes that molecular reference control materials, developed using the most prevalent CPE target genes, and formulated at clinically relevant concentrations, will demonstrate consistent and reliable performance across multiple molecular diagnostic platforms. These platforms include the Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay as well as other PCR methodologies that are commonly employed in public health laboratories. The control materials can therefore support assay validation, enhance diagnostic practices and contribute to improved laboratory performance.

Chapter 2

Assay Design, Optimisation & Feasibility

2.0 Assay Design, Optimisation & Feasibility

2.1 Introduction

CPE can be diagnosed by collecting and testing clinical samples including faecal, blood, urine, or wound swabs (Trepanier et al., 2016). In a clinical setting screening can also take place for patients who have signs and symptoms of infection or who have been at elevated risk of developing CPE infections, for example hospital wards where there has been a CPE outbreak.

Following literature review of CPE detection methods and of External Quality Assessment (EQA) programmes, which can also be referred to as proficiency testing (PT), it was decided to conduct laboratory experiments using qPCR methodologies, with the use of in-house assays (IHAs). Although a range of commercial assays are available for routine testing of CPE, it would not be financially feasible to use commercial kits for routine testing. External database of EQA programmes were reviewed, data gathered was used to identify the key CPE target gene sequences of interest. The information gathered allowed for the development of internal qPCR assays allowed for clinically relevant levels of detection by laboratories to be determined. Additionally, the development of the final control(s) is supported with this information.

EQA programmes can provide a range of samples that are designed to mimic clinical materials, these programmes play a vital role in the quality control of laboratory testing methodologies. They support improved quality control by identifying inaccuracies or inconsistencies in methodologies, assess performance and assay robustness in relation to clinically relevant samples, comply with regulatory and accreditation requirements, and they can highlight areas of poor performance (Badrick, Punyalack and Graham, 2018).

Both clinical and research laboratories can use these EQA schemes to assess their routine testing procedures by an external agency and participation is considered a prerequisite for accreditation by International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 15189 and ISO 17025 guidelines. (Payne et al., 2020).

Participating in relevant EQAs is a crucial element that allows laboratories to effectively manage their testing procedures and is supported by accreditation organizations such as United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS). ISO 15189:2012

(clause 5.6.3.1) requires participation in "interlaboratory comparison programs" which can include EQA programs (UKAS, 2017).

EQA programmes are intended to assess laboratory testing procedures, monitor and improve laboratory quality and highlight systemic issues that occur with the use of test kits or testing platforms. Routine assays are used to assess the samples provided in an EQA and once results are submitted, laboratories are provided a report from the EQA provider.

These reports provide an essential feedback tool for laboratories to evaluate the effectiveness of their detection systems. EQA providers compile data gathered from all participating laboratories and score them based on their performance. The reports detail an evaluation of each of the laboratory's results in comparison to other laboratories in their peer group. First an assigned value and standard deviation is set by the provider for each sample within an EQA panel. Laboratories are scored based on how they report results and how far away from the assigned value they are. This is done by evaluating how well detection of an analyte within a sample has been measured.

Kristensen and Meijer, 2017 provides a detailed review of EQA result interpretation, highlighting the use of Z-scores as a standardised measurement of laboratory performance, utilised to evaluate how accurate laboratories perform against expected results. Z-scores are widely recognised as one of the most commonly used metrics in proficiency testing, and re calculated based on how many standard deviations reported results are from the assigned average value. According to the WHO 2016, Z-scores offer a reliable method for assessing the accuracy of laboratory performance, scores are assigned to participants based on how close submitted data is to the expected assigned values, a score close to zero demonstrates precise testing methodologies.

The interpretation of Z-scores typically follows the criteria set out below (WHO 2016, Kristensen and Meijer, 2017):

- Satisfactory or acceptable results fall within -2.0 to +2.0 suggest the methodology used for detection is precise and no actions are required to improve testing processes.

- Questionable results between -3.0 to -2.0 and 2.0 and 3.0 indicate moderate assay performance requiring review.
- Unsatisfactory or unacceptable results are indicated by a score ranging from ≤ -3.0 or ≥ 3.0 , whereby assay investigation and corrective actions are required to improve performance.

It is essential that EQA providers determine the assigned value accurately with a suitable range to ensure that laboratory performance is accurately assessed, providing reliable data that can highlight poor performance accurately. It is fundamental to have a sufficient number of data sets to obtain reliable estimates to calculate these performance scores. Any anomalies or outliers that could skew data must be identified to ensure correct evaluation (Coucke and Soumali, 2017).

Implementing the use of EQA schemes can be beneficial to enhance the effectiveness of testing methods and laboratory quality. EQA providers distribute schemes with the aim of continuous improvements in testing methods being made and the evaluation of laboratory performance in comparison to that of their peers. EQA's can also lead to improved methodologies by highlighting common errors, thus for clinical laboratories this leads to greater understanding of the prevalence of infectious diseases and therefore improved patient care and outbreak control (Laudus et al 2022).

One aim of the project was to develop in-house qPCR assays for the selected CPE targets of interest; this chapter explores the initial steps taken in assay design and development. It is important to note that the term Cq (Cycle quantification) is used interchangeably with Ct (Cycle threshold) throughout this report. A successful assay must be target specific and able to successfully amplify genes of interest, to do so specific primer and probes are required.

2.1.1 Objectives of Chapter

The first objective of this chapter was to conduct a review of the 'big 5' carbapenemases, namely KPC, IMP, VIM, NDM and OXA-48 in order to find primers and probes that could be used within the in-house assay. Oligonucleotides (oligos), also referred to as primers and probes, are one of the main components of PCR and should be complementary to target DNA region of interest.

Primer sequences must be designed to efficiently bind to their target regions with high specificity (Lorenz 2012). To achieve this, primers and probes were designed to be complementary to specific sequences for the target of interest.

The design process was guided by foundational principles set out by Dieffenbach, Lowe and Dveksler in 1993, who outline key principles for oligonucleotides. These principles have since been refined and optimised. Lorenz 2012 further supports the application of these optimised guidelines to improve amplification efficiency. The following parameter were carefully considered during the design process:

- **GC content:** The proportion of guanine (G) and cytosine (c), i.e. the GC content is recommended to be between 40 and 60%.
- **Avoidance of primer-dimer formulations:** Minimising self-complementarity and cross-complementarity.
- **Primer Length:** Primer should be designed to have around 18-30 bases.
- **Melting temperature (T_m):** Primers optimised with a T_m in the range of 65-75°C

The second objective of this chapter was to establish performance criteria parameters to ensure validity of results obtained. Each of the following parameters were carefully considered to ensure that the assays that are developed are suitable, verified and fit for purpose.

- Each assay must reliably detect the target of interest.
- Assay sensitivity established with Limit of Detection (LoD) and Limit of Quantification(LoQ) determined via the assessment of suitable dilution series.
- Negative samples must be clear of amplification signals or below the Limit of detection.
- Each assay should have specific amplification, with any cross reactivity clearly highlighted.

- Assays should demonstrate a linear relationship across a dilution series with a coefficient of determination (R^2) value of ≥ 0.95 , indicating a strong correlation and consistent assay performance.
- Assays must demonstrate high reproducibility, with consistency performance across test runs and operators. Consistency in assay performance will be evaluated by calculating the standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (%RSD) across replicates. Lower values indicating higher reproducibility and reliability of assay performance.

The third objective of this chapter was to assess the performance of the developed assays. Plasmid dilutions for each target were also assessed. Initial testing was carried out to establish if the reagents selected and methodologies chosen are appropriate and capable of providing desired results.

2.2 Methods

EQA performance reports were reviewed and assessed, to identify CPE biological materials at clinically relevant concentrations. Information gathered allowed suitable materials to be selected for the development of the CPE positive control material.

2.2.1 Oligonucleotide Design and Development

The primers and probes (shown in Table 2) were designed and selected based on literature review prior to the project starting. They were ordered from an external genomic provider (Eurofins Genomic). Lyophilized primers and probes were reconstituted in Tris EDTA (TE) buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0) 0.1 mM EDTA (ThermoFisher Scientific)) to a concentration of 100µM in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions to make master stock vials, in Amber tubes and stored at -80°C. Working stock vials were prepared from the master stocks to a concentration of 10µM for use in master mix preparations during qPCR testing.

Table 2. Oligonucleotides Used in the Development of In-House Assays.

Target	Oligo	Seq (5' > 3')	NCBI Reference
KPC	Forward	GGCCGCCGTGCAATAC	CP125089.1
	Reverse	GCCGCCCAACTCCTCA	
	Probe	[FAM]TGATAACGCCGCCGCCAATTTGT[BHQ1]	
VIM	Forward	AATGCGCAGCACCAGGATAG	CP124659.1
	Reverse	GTTGGTCGCATATCGCAAC	
	Probe	[FAM] TGCCACCCCAGCCGCCCG[BHQ1]	
NDM	Forward	CGCATGCAGCGCGTCCAT	CP124177.1
	Reverse	GACCGCCCAGATCCTCAA	
	Probe	[HEX]TGATCTCCTGCTTGATCCA[BHQ1]	
OXA-48	Forward	TGTTTTGGTGGCATCGAT	CP124179.1
	Reverse	GTAAMRATGCTTGGTTCGC	
	Probe	[HEX]GGAATGCTCACTTACTG[BHQ1]	
IMP	Forward	GAATAGAGTGGCTTAATTCTC	CP119681.1
	Reverse	CCAACCACTAGGTTATC	
	Probe	[FAM]ATTCCCACGTATGCATCTG[BHQ1]	

2.2.2 Master Mix Preparation

All qPCR experiments were performed with a PCR master mix prepared using Qiagen Quantifast Pathogen PCR kit (Catalog 211352) and the target specific primers and probes as shown in Table 3. Each assay PCR master mix was prepared in Amber vials to preserve content integrity, with reagents that had been thawed at room temperature, vortexed and centrifuged prior to use. The reaction setup took place with use of a cool rack to maintain a consistent temperature below 4°C. The total number of reactions was multiplied by the volume per reaction to give the total volume required for inclusion in the master mix. Once the master mix was prepared, 15µl was added to individual wells of 96 well PCR plates and 10µl of template (extracted sample target DNA, No Template Control (NTC) or Plasmid material) was added to a final volume of 25µl. The PCR plate was sealed and centrifuged briefly before placing into PCR machine.

Table 3. qPCR Master Mix Preparation

Internal control (IC) was included only in assays designed with FAM detector dye (KPC, VIM and IMP). For assays designed with HEX detector dye (OXA-48 and NDM), no IC was added to mastermix preparations.

Reagents	Stock Concentration (µM)	Final Concentration (nM)	Volume per Reaction (µL/rxn)
Quantifast Pathogen Master Mix	5 x	1 x	5.00
ROX Dye Solution	50 x	1 x	0.50
Internal Control Assay	10 x	1 x	2.50
Forward Primer Working Stock	10µM	400	1.00
Reverse Primer Working Stock	10µM	400	1.00
Probe Working Stock	10µM	200	0.50
Molecular Grade Water	1x	1x	4.5

2.2.3 DNA Extraction

BioMérieux's® EMAG®, an automated nucleic acid extraction system, was used throughout all testing to isolate nucleic acids from biological samples. The system makes use of magnetic silica-based extraction technology (BOOM® technology) and is used for the universal extraction of RNA and DNA. All extractions conducted processed biological stock materials selected from internal samples, process for extractions were set up in the same way, 6µL Internal Control (IC) DNA, which uses HEX as the detector dye, was first added to the extraction column on EMAG® sample vessels, next 200µL of sample material was added to the vessels according to manufactures instructions. Lysis of samples was performed on board the instrument in 2mL of lysis buffer and incubated for 10 minutes. The instrument added 50µL of Magnetic silica beads to each of the sample columns. Nucleic acid samples were then retrieved in 60µL of elution buffer. Each extraction process had an extraction negative control sample (no biological material included) that was used to identify any issues that could arise during the extraction process and identify contamination. After the extraction of the samples the DNA template was then processed for amplification.

2.2.4 Template Addition and Amplification

15µL of the target assay master mix, prepared as described by Table 4 and 10µL of nucleic acid eluate were dispensed into 96-well PCR plates, resulting in a final volume of 25µL. An NTC was included which used molecular grade water in place of template allowing for any contamination or cross reactivity to be highlighted, as positive NTC results indicates potential contamination. NTC and extraction negative controls were included in all reaction set ups to ensure that any false positives or negatives were detected. PCR plates were then sealed with a self-adhesive optically clear polyolefin sealing film (Starlab). The 96-well plates were then centrifuged at 2000rpm for 2 minutes, to ensure that all reaction mixes contained within the wells were at the bottom of the well.

The Applied Biosystems™ 7500 Real-Time PCR and Bio-Rad CFX96 Touch™ Real-Time PCR instruments were used for amplification of the PCR reaction prepared in section 2.2.4 above using the following DNA cycling conditions.

Table 4. qPCR Amplification Cycling Conditions.

Step			Time	Temperature		
Step 1		1-step cycle				
	Initial PCR step	activation		5 mins	95°C	
Step 2		2-step cycle for 45 cycles				
	Denaturation			15s	95°C	
	Annealing/extension			33s	60°C	Detection is read at this step

2.2.5 Data Analysis

Applied Biosystems™ 7500 Real-Time PCR software and CFX Manager™ Software were used to assess PCR reactions. Throughout testing both instruments have been used to carry out PCR amplification and show comparable results. On completion of a PCR run linear scale was used to visualize amplification curves. Sigmodal amplification curves providing a Ct value were considered positive as these results show that target is present in the reaction well. Reaction wells with weak fluorescent signals or no Ct value presented were considered as being below the detection limit of the assay under evaluation.

The threshold (fluorescent value) was manually adjusted above any background signal and set below plateau phase within the exponential phase to establish Ct values. These are determined based on where the amplification curve crosses the threshold line. The ABI software also allows the manual adjustment of plate baseline. The amplification plot is displayed with the vertical (Y) axis shows fluorescent units (ΔR_n) and the horizontal (X) axis showing PCR Cycle number for the ABI 7500 instrument. However, CFX Manager displays the amplification plot with Relative Fluorescence units (RFU) labelled as the Y axis.

Data was exported to Microsoft Excel where the cycle threshold values were analysed. Qualitative assessment took place where samples assessed in at least two replicates (N=2) had data analysis performed to determine mean cycle threshold (Ct) values, standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (%RSD). Quantitative

assessment included calculating mean quantity value, quantity \log_{10} value as well as \log_{10} mean, SD and %RSD. %RSD gave an indication of the relative accuracy of the result so replicates with a %RSD value below 5% were considered acceptable. A result of >5% RSD suggests variation between the reactions indicating poor operator pipetting techniques or could suggest the sample is at the assay limit of detection (LoD) or limit of quantitation (LoQ).

Where negative samples (extraction negative and NTC) showed amplification signals this suggested contamination had occurred. NTC positive signals indicate contamination in the PCR reaction. Positive signals in extraction negative samples suggest contamination at the extraction stage if NTC is negative. Where both negative reactions do not produce amplification signals the validity of the run can be assured.

2.2.6 Design of Plasmid Constructs to Develop Quantitative In-House Assays

The generation of plasmid constructs allows the in-house assays to be made quantitative, providing a tool to quantify test samples, characterise and quantify biological materials, and thus allow comparison of data between different laboratories and workflows. Points of the dilution series were selected to form Quality Standards (QS) which have known concentrations.

The QS can be used as a reference standard to provide quantitative results; A standard curve represents the relationship between known concentrations and fluorescence (Ct), production of a standard line equation is used to calculate the quantitative value of unknown samples. All quantities determined by this method are relative to the quantities assigned to the standard curve (Sivaganesan et al., 2010).

Plasmid constructs were designed to include sequences from one of the five genes of interest, including the primer and probe binding sites. Target regions were identified using Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST), which confirmed the specificity of the primers and ensured accurate selection of target gene sequence for inclusion. An in-house cassette sequence was designed to include a T7 promoter and Kozak sequence. The inclusion of the T7 promoter is particularly advantageous, as highlighted in Komura et al., 2018 due to its compatibility with standard lab procedures, its ability for efficiently synthesise RNA and DNA templates and be recognised by T7 polymerase. Acevedo et al., 2018 highlights the advantages of

including Kozak sequence as it plays a pivotal role in translation initiation, making it an important feature in synthetic biology applications.

Additionally, a control amplicon sequence based on a non-human target Salmonid Alphavirus (SAV), was also included in the cassette sequence as an internal QC marker. This control amplicon sequence provides a secondary sequence for amplification allowing it to be utilized during troubleshooting assessments and provide direct comparison between the two targets and verification of value assignment by digital PCR. This is included as it can be used in testing if any problems arise when assessing the plasmid and allows the construct to be characterised using either target.

Each target specific sequence was inserted into the cassette sequence, resulting in the design of five distinct plasmid sequences. Figure 5, represents the plasmid map and Table 5 details the gene sequence for each of the assays and the regions where the target specific primer and probe bind have been highlighted.

Table 5. Gene Sequence of Plasmids Showing Primer and Probe Binding Sites.

The forward primer binding site is highlighted in yellow, the probe binding site in purple and the reverse primer binding site in blue.

Target Name/ Accession number	Gene Sequence code
KPC/GenBank: CP125089.1	GCGGAGCTGTCCGC GGCCGCCGTGCAATACAG TGATAACGCCGCCGCCAATTGTG C TGAAGGAGTTGGGCGGC CCGGCCGGGCTGACGGCCTTCATGCGCTCTATCGGCGAT ACCAC
VIM/GenBank: CP124659.1	CATAGAGCACACTCGCAGACGGGACGTACACAATAAGTTGTCGGTCCG AATGCGCAGC ACCAGGATAG AAGAGTCTACTGGACCGAAGCGCACTGCGTCCCCGCTCGATGAGAGT CCTTCTAGAGAGTGCCTGGGAATCTCGTCCCTCTACCTCGGCTAGCCGGCGTGTGAC GGTGATGCGTACGTT TGCCACCCAGCCGCCCG AAGGACATCAACGCCGCCGACGCG GTCGTCATGAAAGTGCCTGGAGACTGCACGCGTTACAGGAAGTCCAATTTGCTTCTCAATC TCCGCGAGAAGTGCCGCTGTGTTTTCGCACCCACGCTGTATCAATCAAAGCAACTCAT CACCATCACGGACAATGAGACCATTGGACGGGTAGACTGCGCCATCAAACGACTGCG GT TGCGATATGCGACCAAAC ACCATCGGCAATCTGGTAAAGCCGGACCTC
NDM/GenBank: CP124177.1	CGCGGTGCTGGTTCGACCCAGCCATTGGCCGGCGAAAGTCAGGCTGTGTTGCGCCGCA ACCATCCCCTCTGCGGGGCAAGCTGGTTCGACAACGCATTGGCATAAGTCGCAATCCC CGC CGCATGCAGCGCGTCCAT ACCGCCATCTTGTCTGATGCGCGTGAGTCACCACC GCCAGCGCGACCGGCAGGTT TGATCTCCTGCTTGATCCA GTTGAGGATCTGGGCGGCTG GTCAT
OXA-48/GenBank: CP124179.1	TG TGTTTTGGTGGCATCGAT TATCGGAATGCCTGCGGTAGCAAAGGAATGGCAAGAAAAC AAAAGTT GGAATGCTCACTTACTG AACATAAATCACAGGGCGTAGTTGTGCTCTGGAATGA GAATAAGCAGCAAGGATTACCAATAATCTTAAACGG GCGAACCAAGCATTTTACC
IMP/GenBank: CP119681.1	GAAATCAAAGGCACTATTTTCATCACATTTCCATAGCGACAGCACAGGAG GAATAGAGTGG CTAATTCTC AATCTATTCCCACGTATGCATCTGAATTAACAAATGAACTTTTGAAAAAATCCGG TAAGGTACAAGCTAAATATTCATTT AGCGAAGTAGCTATTGG CTAGTAAAAATAAAATTGAA GTTTTCTACCCTGGCCCAGGTCACACTCAA GATAACCTAGTGGTTGG TTG

Following design of each of the plasmid their sequences were provided to Eurofins genomics to generate the final plasmid constructs. The target amplicon sequence for each target of interest was designed to be contained within a standard plasmid vector, Figure 5 depicts KPC Plasmid. VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP plasmids were produced in the same manner.

Figure 5. KPC Plasmid Map (pEX-A128-CPE KPC).

This figure depicts the location of the gene of interest within the plasmid vector.

Lyophilised plasmid were reconstituted in 1ml of 1 x TE buffer (Thermofisher). Following this a 10-fold serial dilution was made and all materials were then stored at -80°C. An example of the serial dilution carried out for the plasmids is depicted in Table 6, which shows the dilution plan used for KPC Plasmid stock (pEX-A128-CPE KPC) once lyophilised stock had been reconstituted. The following plasmid stocks were diluted in the same fashion: VIM Plasmid Stock (pEX-A128-CPE VIM), NDM Plasmid Stock (pEX-A128-CPE NDM), OXA-48 Plasmid Stock (pEX-A128-CPE OXA-48) and IMP Plasmid Stock (pEX-A128-CPE IMP).

Table 6. 10-Fold Serial Dilution Plan for KPC Plasmid Stock (pEX-A128-CPE KPC).

Table comprises of Log_{10} increments in a 9-point dilution series. All concentrations are in arbitrary units (AU/ml).

Step	Start Concentration (AU/ml)	Stock Vol	Diluent Volume (TE Buffer) (mL)	Total (mL)	Ratio	New Concentration (AU/ml)	Use in Next Step (mL)	Batch Code
1	1.00E+09	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+08	0.05	p/KPC/A
2	1.00E+08	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+07	0.05	p/KPC/B
3	1.00E+07	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+06	0.05	p/KPC/C
4	1.00E+06	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+05	0.05	p/KPC/D
5	1.00E+05	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+04	0.05	p/KPC/E
6	1.00E+04	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+03	0.05	p/KPC/F
7	1.00E+03	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+02	0.05	p/KPC/G
8	1.00E+02	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+01	0.05	p/KPC/H
9	1.00E+01	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+00	0	p/KPC/I

2.2.7 Assay Optimisation

Each plasmid dilution series was evaluated by qPCR using the target specific in-house assay. Available biological material (EQA test samples) was assessed under specific testing methodologies as previously described, where each sample was extracted once and amplified in three replicates. KPC, VIM and IMP targets have been designed with the target dye FAM, NDM and OXA-48 fluorescent dye is HEX. The Qiagen PCR kit used amplifiers the Internal control (IC) target on HEX dye, therefore no IC was added to NDM and OXA-48 targets as this would interfere with the target dye.

2.2.7.1 IMP Assay Optimisation SYBR

Further optimisation of the IMP assay was required, see results section 2.3. Investigation to assess the compatibility of the IMP primers designed was conducted by using SYBR Green, a fluorescent dye that binds to double-stranded DNA and is amplified with use of PCR (Wittwer et al., 1997).

Testing with QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Kit (Catalog 208252) was performed. The kit enables master mix to be prepared without the need for a target specific probe; therefore, the performance of the primers can be established. If amplification occurs with use of the SYBR probe this is conclusive that the primers are able to detect target gene of interest.

Each master mix was prepared in a similar fashion to section 2.2.2 above. The total number of reactions was multiplied by the volume per reaction to give the total volume required for inclusion in the master mix. Once the master mix bulk was prepared this was moved through the workflow with 18µl added to individual wells of 96 well PCR plates and 2µl of target DNA was added to a final volume of 20µl.

Table 7. QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Master Mix Preparation.

Rox dye use within the master mix is not compatible for amplification on CFX.

Reagents	Stock Concentration (µM)	Final Concentration	Volume per Reaction (µL/rxn)
2 x QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Master Mix	2 x	1 x	10.00
ROX Reference Dye (ABI cycler only)	1x	1 x	0.10
Forward Primer Working Stock	10µM	0.7µM	1.40
Reverse Primer Working Stock	10µM	0.7µM	1.40
Molecular Grade Water	1x	1x	5.10

Applied Biosystems™ 7500 Real-Time PCR and Bio-Rad CFX96 Touch™ Real-Time PCR instruments were used for amplification using the conditions shown in Table 8 below.

Table 8. QuantiNova SYBR Green PCR Amplification Conditions.

Step		Time	Temperature	
Step 1	1-step cycle			
	Initial PCR activation step	2 mins	95°C	
Step 2	2-step cycle for 40 cycles			
	Denaturation	5 secs	95°C	
	Annealing/extension	33 secs	60°C	Detection is read at this step

2.2.7.2 IMP Assay Optimisation Temperature Gradient

Gradient PCR testing was conducted, to allow assessment of the probe across a temperature gradient to determine the most optimal annealing temperature. A range of different annealing temperatures were used including 60°C, 55°C and 50.6°C allowing assessment of the probes binding efficiency and specificity under caring temperatures.

2.2.7.3 IMP Assay Optimisation Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R Assay

To ensure that the sample material evaluated on the IMP in-house assay was suitable for use with the target assay, a commercial assay, Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay was employed to perform testing on the IMP sample. As described in Section 1.8.4.3 above 1.7ml of sample was prepared and dispensed into a Carba-R cartridge and assessed with the Cepheid instrument.

2.2.7.4 IMP Assay Optimisation Probe Redesign

IMP probe was redesigned ensuring that the sequence was still within the selected plasmid sequence (GenBank: CP119681.1). The testing was conducted using extracted material and the full plasmid dilution sequence.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Assessment of EQA Data

Analysis of the EQA data showed that the five resistance genes; Imipenem-resistant Pseudomonas (IMP), Klebsiella pneumoniae carbapenemase (KPC), New Delhi Metallo- β -lactamases (NDM) Verona integron-encoded Metallo- β -lactamases (VIM) and OXA-48-type carbapenem-hydrolysing class D β -lactamase (OXA-48) were correctly detected positive by over 93% of participants. Samples from the 2019 and 2021 EQA programs shown in Table 9 below were selected for use in this project. Table 9 lists the EQA programmes which were investigated to select candidate material for testing.

Table 9. EQA Programmes

List of programmes examined to find candidate material for the development of CPE controls.

Year	Panel Code
2017	2017 Extended Spectrum β - lactamase and Carbapenemase EQA Programme
2019	2019 Extended Spectrum β - lactamase and Carbapenemase EQA Programme
2020	2020 Extended Spectrum β - lactamase and Carbapenemase EQA Programme
2021	2021 Extended Spectrum β - lactamase and Carbapenemase EQA Programme
2022	2022 Extended Spectrum β - lactamase and Carbapenemase EQA Programme

Table 10. EQA Performance Data from Assessed CPE Biological Stocks.

Target Name	Detected (%)	Not Detected (%)	Not tested (%)
KPC	96.7	0.0	3.3
VIM	95.8	0.0	4.2
NDM	94.2	3.3	2.5
OXA-48	95.0	2.50	2.5
IMP	98.7	1.3	0.0

2.3.2 Feasibility Results

The initial feasibility testing results of the five CPE assays using biological stock material is illustrated in Figure 6, where amplification plots are presented for each assay. Table

11 provides the corresponding Ct value \pm SD result for both target and internal control results. The internal control results for KPC, VIM and IMP targets were consistent demonstrating that efficient DNA extraction had been conducted. However, IC results were not applicable for NDM and OXA-48 assays, as IC detector dye (VIC) shares the same fluorescent channel as the target dye (HEX) and was therefore not included in master mix preparation for these assays.

The results demonstrate that all assays except IMP were able to accurately detect targets of interest and produce sigmoidal amplification curves. Replicate results were within a suitable Ct range with SD results below 1SD and %RSD values below 5%, indicating strong reproducibility. Additionally, negative controls did not exhibit amplification curves that crossed the threshold, supporting the feasibility of the assay designs. Figures 6A-D display amplification on CFX platform and Figure 6E displays amplification with ABI 7500.

Table 11. Primer & Probe Feasibility Results for In-House Assays

Target Name	Mean Ct Value \pm SD. N=3	Mean IC Ct Value \pm SD. N=3
KPC	17.30 \pm 0.02	31.21 \pm 0.10
VIM	16.45 \pm 0.11	31.63 \pm 0.50
NDM	18.97 \pm 0.25	Not applicable
OXA-48	17.36 \pm 0.11	Not applicable
IMP	Amplification Failure	30.04 \pm 0.10

Figure 6. Primer & Probe Feasibility Results In-House Assays

Panels 6A to 6D show amplification curves for KPC, VIM, NDM and OXA-48 assays on the CFX instrument (RFU), with biological samples, extraction negative controls (NCs) and NTC's displaying typical sigmoidal curves. Panel 6E presents IMP assay data from the ABI 7500(ΔRn), lacking the expected sigmoidal pattern.

2.3.3 IMP Assay Results

During initial testing the IMP assay did not yield viable amplification results as illustrated in Figure 6(E), where no amplification curve is observed. To investigate this further, conformation testing was conducted using the Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay to assess the performance of the selected IMP biological material. As shown in Table 12, the GeneXpert platform successfully detected the IMP gene while VIM, NDM, KPC, and OXA-48 were not detected.

Additionally, the positive control sample later discussed in Chapter 3 was also assessed on this platform and yielded a positive result for IMP, reinforcing the conclusion that the failure of the initial In-House Assay (IHA) was likely due to assay-specific limitations rather than the quality of the biological material.

Table 12. IMP of Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R Assay Results.

Number of tests performed for each sample was 1 and is noted as (N=1)

Sample Reference	Ct Value (Cepheid) N=1	Analyte Detection
IMP Biological Sample Dilution point A	18.8	IMP Detection Only
CPE PC Sample (Containing IMP Biological Sample Dilution point C)	25.4	IMP Detected VIM Detected NDM Detected KPC Detected OXA-48 Detected
CPE PC Sample (1in10) (Containing IMP Biological Sample Dilution point C)	30.5	IMP Detected VIM Detected NDM Detected KPC Detected OXA-48 Detected

Figure 7. Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay Result Amplification Graph for IMP Sample Dilution Point A.

The next step of IHA development was to assess the performance of IMP primers. The SYBR Green testing carried out showed the primers performed successfully. Figure 8 below shows the amplification curve produced for this testing. IMP Biological Sample Dilution point A amplified at Ct of 20.18 ± 0.05 . For this data set, IMP Sample Dilution point A was assessed in two replicates. Validity of results was confirmed with NTC and extraction negative, which did not produce amplification signals. Results obtained showed that the negative controls did not have any amplification signals.

Figure 8. IMP SYBR Green Results

The graph displays the sigmoidal amplification curve produced by IMP Biological Dilution Point A, Extraction Negative control (NC) and NTC.

Following this the performance of the probe was assessed with a temperature gradient PCR run. However, amplification was not achieved for any of the tested conditions as depicted by Figure 9 below. The limited range of annealing temperature assessed may not have been inclusive of the true optimal temperature. Further testing utilising a broader or refined temperature range could identify the optimal temperature. Additionally, only one temperature gradient run was performed and it would be advantageous for this experimental run to be repeated to confirm results. This error therefore did not rule out the possibility that operator errors or technical variability influenced the results. Despite these limitations the decision was made to redesign the probe, which allowed the project to proceed with a more reliable and effective probe selection.

Figure 9. IMP Temperature Gradient Amplification Plot.

Following IMP probe redesign (described by section 2.2.7.4), feasibility testing was performed. The test results from Table 13 and Figure 10 shows the performance of the IMP assay with use of the redesigned probe. The results demonstrate that the IMP assay, with use of the new probe can successfully amplify IMP biological sample material.

Table 13. IMP New Probe Feasibility Result

Number of replicates performed for each sample was 2 and is noted as (N=2)

Sample Name	Mean Ct Value± SD. N=2	Mean IC Ct Value± SD. N=2
IMP Sample Dilution Point D	31.36±0.15	29.93±0.05
CPE PC Sample (1in100) (Containing IMP Sample Dilution point C)	39.24±1.66	29.96±0.06

Figure 10. qPCR Amplification of IMP Extracted Samples

Results with new probe sequence. The graph displays the amplification curve of: CPE PC Feasibility sample 1in100, IMP Biological Dilution Point D, Extraction Negative control (NC) and NTC.

The linearity of the plasmid dilution series (described in section 2.2.6) were assessed and displayed in Figure 11. The standard curve graphs depict the relationship between the observed Ct value (Y axis) and the plasmid concentration (X axis). As described in Section 2.2.1, to confirm a linear relationship the coefficient of determination (R^2) value must be ≥ 0.95 . The line equation $Y = AX + B$ is derived by analysing the dilution series. Where 'Y' represents the Ct value, 'A' is the slope, 'B' is the interception line and 'X' is the \log_{10} dc/ml concentration value.

(A) KPC

(B) VIM

(C) NDM

(D) OXA-48

(E) IMP

Figure 11. Plasmid Dilution Linearity In-House CPE Assays.

Panels 11A-11E show standard curves for KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP assays, demonstrating linear dilution series generated.

2.4 Discussion

The primary objective of this project was to produce CPE reference control materials that aid laboratories with assessing performance of molecular assays at every stage, from nucleic acid extraction through to amplification and detection. In Chapter 2, the project investigated relevant EQA data and literature to identify the most prevalent carbapenemase genes. Building on this, qualitative in-house qPCR assays were subsequently designed and developed to enable accurate detection of these genes.

Naruemit Sayabovorn et al., 2025 highlights the prevalence of acquired CRE in a hospital setting was 16.4% among all isolates studied. A total of 20,544 acquired CPO isolates were reported in England from October 2020 to December 2024, with an overall annual rate of 13.0 per 100,000 population in 2024 (UK Health Security Agency, 2024). Therefore, accurate detection of CPE is essential to allow for actions to be taken to combat outbreaks and to limit the spread of resistant genes.

Literature review and investigation of suitable CPE Genes indicated that there were 5 carbapenemase enzymes of interest that have been named 'the big five' and include KPC, IMP, VIM, NDM and OXA-48. Due to their global prevalence, these resistance genes are considered a significant threat to public health due to their resistance to antibiotics (Kubota et al., 2018).

Appropriate oligonucleotide sequences were selected and optimised for the 'big five' CPE genes allowing some of the most prevalent carbapenemases to be considered (Mentasti et al., 2019). The inclusion of the most prevalent genes within the proposed molecular reference control, will allow it to be utilized by various laboratories around the world as they can assess their testing platforms capabilities to detect the CPE genes that are most commonly detected.

Examination of EQA reports was conducted to select biological stocks that produce positive results $\geq 93\%$ of the time. Prior to commencing any procedures in the laboratory, EQA reports were gathered and reviewed to select appropriate materials to be utilised in the development of positive control materials. The reports examined provided information regarding the performance of participating laboratories and their ability to detect β -lactamase and carbapenemase coding genes in a clinical setting using their routine molecular diagnostic procedures. The information gathered

provided a guideline of the appropriate levels of detection required within laboratories and thus was the starting point in developing a molecular reference control for CPE. It is vital to provide controls that can be detected in laboratories performing testing with a range of different methodologies.

Results are categorised based on the workflow used and the resistance gene(s) detected, EQA reports give an indication of laboratories' ability to detect biological materials in a clinical setting using their routine molecular diagnostic procedures. Based on workflow used, participants are grouped and provided with a report in comparison to laboratories who have used a similar testing procedure.

In 2021, 122 participating laboratories from 29 countries received the 2021 ESBL panel. Only 107 respondents returned data for analysis, with 153 datasets submitted, showing an 89.2% return rate. 15 participants did not return results. Data returned for each sample in the EQA panel was subdivided into groups based on the technology used; for example, the KPC sample data included the following information from a total of 116 datasets 19 stated that in-house testing methods were used (16.4%), and 97 stated commercial was the technology used (83.6%).

The development of in-house qPCR assays for the CPE target genes was initiated and feasibility testing results illustrate that oligonucleotides and suitable clinical materials have been selected for each of the 5 target gene assays.

Table 11 details the performance of CPE assays for primer / probe feasibility testing conducted. Four of the five assays (KPC, VIM, NDM and OXA-48) displayed sigmoidal amplification signals as shown by Figure 6. This demonstrates that the primers and probes designed for each of these targets can successfully amplify targets of interest.

IC results were consistent for IMP qPCR amplification as represented in Table 11, proving that DNA was efficiently extracted, however the target sample selected did not produce amplification of selected materials as depicted by Figure 6(E), no sigmoidal amplification curves were observed. The IMP assay was further developed as described in section 2.3.

First, an assessment of the biological material selected for use with the IMP IHA was conducted, in order to ensure that there are no misgivings regarding biological materials. Commercially available Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay was used to assess the presence of CPE. As shown in Table 12, the assay successfully detected IMP

Target in the IMP Biological Sample Dilution Point A, with no cross reactivity observed for the other carbapenemase genes included in the assay. This result supports the specificity of the assay, demonstrating that IMP was accurately detected without producing false positives for the other genes. This finding validates the suitability of the selected biological samples for use in assay development. However, additional work was necessary to optimise the in-house PCR assay.

As the Cepheid Carba-R assay required a sample input volume of 1.7mL to perform 1 reaction, the biological EQA material was diluted to allow suitable volumes to be available. Only a limited number of samples could be assessed at this stage due to material and Cepheid cartridge availability. This analysis is qualitative only and provides a Ct value for positive amplification. Results show that the IMP analyte was detected successfully; Figure 7 depicts the amplification plot produced by the Cepheid instrument for IMP Sample Dilution point A result. A sigmoidal amplification curve is observed for IMP target only and VIM, NDM, KPC, and OXA-48 were not detected. These findings demonstrate that the biological material used for IMP assay development is successfully detected with the use of a commercial Carbapenemase assay and so should be suitable for use in the development of IMP IHA.

SYBR Green assessment with IMP primers proved successful. Figure 8 shows the successful amplification curve produced. Considering that the primers were able to amplify the IMP biological material this concluded that the amplification issues observed (Figure 6) was due to performance of the probe which then required further development.

Finally, the CPE assays were further developed, with the design of plasmid constructs, plasmid material was utilised to act as reference standards on all in-house assay qPCR test runs. These plasmids allowed consistent quantification and validation of assay performance. As shown in Figure 11, each of the dilution series demonstrated clear linearity. The relationship between the Ct value and plasmid concentration was based on the line equation $Y=AX+B$, as described in section 2.3.3 above.

The slope of the line reflects the efficiency of the PCR reaction with a value of -3.3 corresponding to 100% efficiency, In Figure 11, the slopes ranged from -3.5 to -3.9, indicating that further optimisation work may be required to improve assay performance. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of each line equation was determined, allowing variation to be assessed, and an R^2 value close to 1 represents

a better correlation coefficient from the slope. It can be concluded that the five plasmid dilution series depicted in Figure 11 are linear as all results are ≥ 0.99 .

The results obtained in section 2.3 demonstrate successful amplification of all five targets of interests. The objective of this chapter, to design and develop qPCR IHA that could be used for the detection of CPE targets, has been achieved. The developed assays have demonstrated the ability to accurately detect targets of interest, thus achieving the objective of the chapter. The results obtained allowed for the study to proceed to the next step where a multiplex PC was formulated, see Chapter 4.

Chapter 3

Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR): Selection and Quantification of Reference Standards

3.0 Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR): Selection and Quantification of Reference Standards

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the characterisation of plasmid materials required to transition the qualitative assays developed in Chapter 2 into quantitative assays. Accurate determination of plasmid concentrations allows the material to be used as reference standards, internally referred to as Quality Standards (QS). These standards are essential for qPCR quantification of unknown biological CPE samples.

Accurate quantification of nucleic acids is a crucial process in PCR. qPCR is a method of nucleic acid quantification; amplification is performed, and nucleic acid concentrations are calculated using standard curves. The standard curve are generated from the testing of a dilution series of material which has known concentrations. These are included on every qPCR run. The Ct values are plotted against the known concentrations of the standards. The correlation between the fluorescence and concentration is determined by the standard curve produced, a line of best fit is produced, and this then allows other test samples on the same qPCR plate to be quantified using the standard curve line equation (Dhanasekaran, Doherty and Kenneth, 2010).

Plasmid materials were chosen to function as reference standards for each CPE IHA designed, concentrations were determined by digital characterisation. A number of laboratories have demonstrated that plasmids are appropriate for use as reference standards (Li et al., 2013, Wu, Z. et al. 2024). ddPCR methodologies allows for the absolute quantification of nucleic acids without the need for reference standards, providing precise concentrations allows for standardisation of data between different laboratories and technologies. (Huggett, Cowen and Foy, 2014). Figure 12 from Li et al., 2018 depicts the comparison of qPCR and ddPCR.

Four plasmid dilution points were selected for use as QS materials based on their alignment with the developed PC and biological sample results. The QS series, that had concentrations determined via ddPCR, was used to generate standard curves in qPCR assessments.

The Bio-Rad QX200 Droplet Digital PCR technology was utilised to perform ddPCR testing, to provide absolute quantification of plasmid materials developed in Chapter

2 providing concentrations in digital copies per microliter(dc/mL). This platform employs water-oil emulsion technology with use of a droplet generator instrument to partition each reaction into up to 20,000 droplets. Amplification occurs in each individual droplet; a droplet reader is utilised to measure the fluorescent signal emitted. Droplets are assessed to determine the presence or absence of target sequence. The number of droplets are counted as positive droplets or negative droplets. If a droplet contains at least one target copy it is determined as a positive droplet and droplets that contain no target copies are assigned as negative. Poisson statistics is employed to determine the ratio of positive to negative droplets, determining the absolute number of target nucleic acid molecules in a sample based on the proportion of positive droplets contained.

The development of the qPCR CPE assays is summarised below:

- **Qualitative Assay Design:** For each of the 'big five' carbapenemase qualitative target specific assays were developed, as outlined in Chapter 2.
- **Plasmid Construct Design:** Plasmid constructs containing the target gene sequence and a secondary QC target sequence were designed to serve as assay controls and reference standards, as described in Chapter 2.
- **PCR evaluation of Plasmid Materials:** Plasmid materials were diluted and assessed alongside biological samples using PCR to ensure suitable plasmid points were selected for use and allowing accurate quantification of test samples.
- **Selection of Plasmids for characterisation:** Plasmid dilution points with a Ct value between 20 and 27 were selected for ddPCR assessment.
- **Absolute Quantification of Plasmid materials via ddPCR:** Plasmid materials were assessed with ddPCR to determine their concentrations.
- **Establishment of Reference standards:** From the dilution series points spaced approximately one logarithmic unit apart were selected as reference standards.

Figure 12. Comparisons of ddPCR and qPCR. (Li et al., 2018)

3.2 Methods

The Bio-Rad QX200 Droplet Digital PCR System consists of two instruments, the QX200 Droplet Generator and the QX200 Droplet Reader.

Points from the plasmid dilution series for each assay that had a Ct result between 20-27 were selected for use in digital droplet PCR testing as this is within the digital dynamic range for the Bio-Rad platform. ddPCR was carried out to give a quantitative value of the plasmid in dc/ml values, allowing for absolute quantitation of nucleic acid.

3.2.1 ddPCR Master Mix and Sample Reaction Preparation

First the ddPCR master mix was prepared, where target specific primers and probes were combined with Bio-Rad ddPCR Supermix for Probes (no dUTP) (Catalog 1863024). The master mix reagent preparation is displayed in Table 14 below. The total number of reactions required plus an additional 2 reactions were multiplied by the volume per run to give a total volume of reagents required.

Table 14. ddPCR Master Mix Contents

Reagents	Start Concentration	Final Concentration	Volume per run ($\mu\text{L}/\text{rxn}$)
2 x ddPCR™ Supermix for Probes (No dUTP)	2x	1x	12.50
Forward Primer	10 μM	0.4 μM	1.00
Reverse Primer	10 μM	0.4 μM	1.00
Probe	10 μM	0.2 μM	0.50
Molecular Grade Water	1x	1x	5.00

Reaction pool mixes were then prepared by combining the master mix and template together, 5 μL of target DNA is combined with 20 μL of master mix in a final volume of 25 μL .

3.2.3 Droplet Generation and PCR Reaction

Droplet generation was performed by loading an 8 well droplet generation DG8 cartridge (Catalog 1864008) with 22 μ L of reaction mix pipetted into the middle wells and 70 μ L of droplet generation oil (Catalog 1863005) was dispensed into the oil wells at the bottom of the cartridge. A DG8 gasket (Catalog 1863009) was placed over the wells and the cartridge loaded onto the droplet generation to allow droplet generation of up to 20,000 droplets per well to take place. Successful droplet generation was demonstrated by the production of droplets in the top wells of the cartridge. From this, 40 μ L was carefully transferred to a 96-well plate, sealed securely with a pierceable foil plate seal (Catalog 1814040) using a PX1 PCR Plate Sealer at 180°C for 5 seconds.

The quality of sample results can be negatively impacted by lysis of the droplets generated; therefore, all experimental work was conducted with care to ensure this was minimized.

Next, an Applied Biosystems™ ABI 2720 Thermal cycler was used to perform PCR reactions.

Table 15. ddPCR Cycling Conditions

Cycling Step	Temperature, °C	Time	Ramp Rate	Number of Cycles
Enzyme Activation	95	10 minutes	2°C/Sec	1
Denaturation	94	30 seconds		40
Annealing/Extension	60	1 minute		1
Enzyme Deactivation	98	10 minutes		1
Cooling Step	12	30 minutes		1
Hold (Optional)	4	Infinite		1

3.2.4 Data Analysis

The QX200 Droplet Reader was used which performs fluorescence analysis. As per the manufactures' instructions, prior to use the droplet reader was 'Primed' with ddPCR droplet reader oil (Catalogue 1863004) to flush the instruments lines and fill them with droplet reader oil to allow optimal results. The 96-well PCR plate was transferred to the instrument. QuantaSoft software was set up in accordance with the experiment type, Absolute quantification (ABS) analysis was selected for all plates whereby the

instrument automatically determines threshold and automatic production of sample concentrations. Manual threshold line settings were also used across all selected wells.

Each droplet is analysed by the instrument individually on a two-channel detection system where FAM dye fluorescence is read on 'Channel 1' and 'Channel 2' reads HEX fluorescence, positive droplets exhibit fluorescence. The reader measures the intensity of fluorescence in every individual droplet with the concentration quantified and given a value in copies of target per microliter (copies/ μ l).

Data was visualized on the software with the use of the 1-D plot amplification, where droplets are plotted with fluorescence intensity on the vertical axis (Amplitude) against droplet numbers along the horizontal axis (Event Number). Any droplets above the automated or manual threshold line are observed as positive and coloured blue (FAM channel) or green (HEX Channel) by the instrument, droplets below the threshold are considered negative and are represented in the colour grey.

Thresholds can be set automatically by the instrument or manually adjusted as required. An example of data produced by the instrument is shown by Figure 13 below.

(A) KPC NTC Sample Well result

(B) KPC plasmid positive point D

(C) KPC Results in wells A01, B01, C01, D01. Threshold line set by instrument

Figure 13. ddPCR Data Analysis Using QuantaSoft Software

(A) KPC NTC Sample well (A01)

(B) KPC plasmid point D sample well (B01)

(C) All KPC sample wells showing where the instrument has set the threshold automatically.

Data was then exported to Microsoft Excel. Any results with an accepted droplet count below 10,000 or concentration below 5 c/mL were excluded from analysis as both criteria indicate the samples are at the LoQ of the digital platform and results are variable.

To calculate digital copies/ml (dc/ml) from the raw digital PCR data obtained a conversion factor was used to back calculate to the starting concentration.

First the 'copies/20 μ L' generated by the instrument were multiplied by 50 to give the value in dc/ml. Back-calculation to determine the sample/stock start concentration was then performed. This was done with the following calculation:

$$\frac{(\text{Value in dc/ml} \times \text{Stock Start Concentration})}{(\text{Stock Final Concentration})}$$

From this the mean back calculation result of each sample was calculated and then a mean of all results was provided. The Log₁₀ dc/ml value of each back calculated value was taken, Grubbs analysis was then performed to determine any outlying results which, if identified, were excluded from data analysis. From this the average Log₁₀ dc/ml result of each sample was calculated and then a mean of all results was provided, standard deviation of the Log₁₀ value was calculated, as well as %RSD.

3.2.5 Troubleshooting

OXA-48 and IMP plasmids failed to amplify using the ddPCR platform with target specific primers and probes after the initial feasibility test run, as well as confirmation ddPCR test run, with use of a range finder test run.

It was decided to evaluate the OXA-48 and IMP plasmids using the control amplicon sequence (SAV), whereby SAV target primers and probes can be utilized for the quantitation of plasmids.

First qPCR testing was conducted to assess the performance of both target and SAV sequences and the ratio between them. This assessment was carried out to extrapolate from ddPCR SAV data that the concentration determined also applies to the target of interest. The comparison between both assays on qPCR ensures that digital values assigned using SAV primers and probes can be used to assign digital values to the target assay if the ratio between the two targets is 1:1. Additionally, a verification sample was prepared, a target plasmid dilution point with a known concentration (quantified using SAV primers and probe on ddPCR) was used to

prepare a verification sample at Log₁₀ 5 dc/ml. Table 16 and 17 below illustrates how these samples were prepared.

Table 16. OXA-48 Log₁₀ 5 dc/ml Plasmid Verification Dilution Plan

Plasmid point OXA-482407032D with an assigned concentration of 1.90E+06 dc/ml (6.28 Log₁₀ dc/ml), was used as the start material.

Step	Start Concentration (dc/mL)	Stock Vol(mL)	Diluent Volume (1xTE Buffer) (mL)	Total (mL)	Ratio	New Concentration (dc/mL)	Use in Next Step (mL)	Batch Code
1	1.90E+06	0.1	0.85	0.95	0.11	2.00E+05	0.02	pOXA-48/E
2	2.00E+05	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	1.00E+05	0.00	pOXA-48/F (Log ₁₀ 5 dc/ml Verification sample)

Table 17. IMP Log₁₀ 5 dc/ml Verification Dilution Plan

Plasmid point IMP2407029D with an assigned concentration of 1.76E+06 dc/ml value (6.25 Log₁₀ dc/ml), was used as the start material.

Step	Start Concentration (dc/mL)	Stock Vol(mL)	Diluent Volume (1xTE Buffer) (mL)	Total (mL)	Ratio	New Concentration (dc/mL)	Use in Next Step (mL)	Batch Code
1	1.76E+06	0.05	0.39	0.44	0.11	2.00E+05	0.02	pIMP/E
2	2.00E+05	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.5	1.00E+05	0.00	pIMP/F (Log ₁₀ 5 dc/ml Verification sample)

3.3 Results

Plasmid dilution points were chosen that were within the dynamic range of the Bio-Rad ddPCR platform. Corresponding qPCR results with Ct values between 20 and 27 were selected to ensure compatibility with the quantification range of the Bio-Rad platform. ddPCR testing was conducted as outlined in section 3.2. Table 18 represents ddPCR data results for each assay.

KPC, VIM and OXA-48 targets were evaluated over a total of three independent ddPCR runs to confirm consistency and ensure reproducibility. A minimum of two test runs were performed. For the IMP assay two batches of plasmid dilution series were prepared and qualified with ddPCR.

Table 18. ddPCR Results Table

Number of replicates performed for each sample noted as (N=X)

Target Name	Test run reference	Mean back calculated value dc/ml	Mean Log ₁₀ (dc/ml)
KPC	ddPCR 2024-033(N=4)	2.56E+10	10.41 ± 0.03
	ddPCR 2024-034(N=3)	1.70E+10	10.23 ± 0.01
	ddPCR 2024-014(N=7)	2.51E+10	10.40 ± 0.02
VIM	ddPCR 2024-033(N=4)	1.46E+10	10.16 ± 0.05
	ddPCR 2024-034(N=2)	1.31E+10	10.13 ± 0.03
	ddPCR 2024-014(N=7)	1.54E+10	10.19 ± 0.01
NDM	ddPCR 2024-034(N=5)	1.28E+10	10.11 ± 0.02
	ddPCR 2025-035(N=6)	1.45E+10	10.16 ± 0.01
OXA-48 (SAV Oligos)	ddPCR 2024-034(N=4)	1.90E+10	10.28 ± 0.01
	ddPCR 2024-035(N=7)	1.79E+10	10.25 ± 0.03
	ddPCR 2025-008(N=7)	1.90E+10	10.28 ± 0.03
IMP (SAV Oligos)	ddPCR 2025-008(N=7)	1.76E+10	10.25 ± 0.01
	ddPCR 2025-010(N=7)	1.94E+10	10.29 ± 0.02
IMP (SAV Oligos) Batch 001	ddPCR 2025-016(N=7)	7.54E+09	9.87 ± 0.05
	ddPCR 2025-017(N=6)	8.00E+09	9.90 ± 0.07
	ddPCR 2025-017(N=7)	8.04E+09	9.90 ± 0.06

3.3.1 Troubleshooting

OXA-48 and IMP targets did not exhibit amplification with target specific primers and probes. Therefore, SAV oligonucleotides were used, to determine plasmid concentrations. As described in section 2.2.6, SAV amplicon sequence is included in the design of target plasmids so can be utilized to assign quantities to plasmid materials.

To use SAV primers and probe to determine the concentration of OXA-48 and IMP plasmid dilutions, the relationship between the performance of the SAV assay and the target assay was determined using qPCR testing. OXA-48 results gathered and displayed by Table 19 show that the performance of the SAV qPCR and the OXA-48 qPCR assays are comparable.

This testing was conducted to accurately compare the performance of the two assays, the Ct values observed for each of the selected plasmid dilution points displayed less than 1 Ct value difference between the two assays. This data demonstrates an approximate 1:1 ratio, which was determined by dividing the concentration detected by the SAV assay with that observed by the OXA-48 assays.

Additionally, Figure 14 shows that the OXA-48 assay results are consistent with SAV assay, both targets had an R^2 value of 0.99, which indicates good linearity between the Ct value and dc/ml value. Similarly, IMP target results, Table 20 and Figure 15 demonstrated that the IMP assay is comparable to the SAV assay, and they have an approximate ratio of 1:1.

To verify the accuracy of concentrations determined using the SAV oligonucleotides verification samples were prepared at a target concentration of $5 \text{ Log}_{10} \text{ dc/mL}$ for both OXA-48 and IMP plasmids. These samples were tested using the developed qPCR assays, and the resulting dc/mL values were calculated using standard curves. The amplification results confirmed that each verification sample performed as expected, with consistent concentrations observed across both assays.

These results show that using SAV secondary target sequence to calculate plasmid quantities of the primary target sequence is valid, supporting the use of generating $\text{Log}_{10} \text{ dc/ml}$ values for both the OXA-48 and the IMP plasmid materials.

Table 19. qPCR Data Comparison Between SAV and OXA-48 Oligonucleotides.

Sample Reference	SAV		OXA-48	
	Mean Ct Value \pm SD.	Log ₁₀ dc/ml Value	Mean Ct Value \pm SD.	Log ₁₀ dc/ml Value
pOXA-48/F (Log ₁₀ 5 dc/ml Verification sample) (N=3)	25.33 \pm 0.40	4.99	25.53 \pm 0.26	4.98
pOXA-48/D (N=2)	20.67 \pm 0.11	6.28	20.96 \pm 0.04	6.28
pOXA-48/E (N=2)	24.26 \pm 0.01	5.28	24.34 \pm 0.32	5.28
pOXA-48/F (N=2)	28.14 \pm 0.32	4.28	27.90 \pm 0.07	4.28
pOXA-48/G (N=2)	31.35 \pm 0.19	3.28	31.80 \pm 0.05	3.28

Figure 14. qPCR Standard Curve Comparison Between SAV and OXA-48 Oligonucleotides.

Table 20. qPCR Data Comparison Between SAV and IMP Oligonucleotides

Sample Reference	SAV		IMP	
	Mean Ct Value ± SD	Log ₁₀ dc/ml Value	Mean Ct Value ± SD	Log ₁₀ dc/ml Value
pIMP/F (Log ₁₀ 5 dc/ml Verification sample (N=3))	25.91 ± 0.32	5.02 ± 0.09	27.20 ± 0.26	4.86 ± 0.16
pIMP/A (N=2)	11.55 ± 0.01	8.98 ± 0.00	12.43 ± 0.35	9.30 ± 0.10
pIMP/B (N=2)	15.20 ± 0.04	7.97 ± 0.01	14.89 ± 0.07	8.26 ± 0.02
pIMP/C (N=2)	18.43 ± 0.28	7.08 ± 0.08	18.54 ± 0.18	7.17 ± 0.05
pIMP/D (N=2)	Sample not assessed	Sample not assessed	21.56 ± 0.34	6.29 ± 0.00
pIMP/E (N=2)	25.12 ± 0.32	5.29 ± 0.00	24.89 ± 1.29	5.29 ± 0.00
pIMP/F (N=2, *N=1))	28.24 ± 1.19	4.29 ± 0.00	29.55*	4.29*
pIMP/G (N=2, *N=1))	32.56*	3.29*	31.74 ± 0.46	3.29 ± 0.00

Figure 15. qPCR Standard Curve Comparison between SAV and IMP Oligonucleotides.

Table 21. Quality Standards Selected for use as Reference Standards
 Number of replicates amplified was two and is noted as (N=2(*N=1)).

Target	Reference Standard	Plasmid Reference	Ct Value	Mean Log ₁₀ (dc/ml)
KPC	Quality Standard 1 (QS1)	pKPC/G	31.51*	3.40 *
	Quality Standard 2 (QS2)	pKPC/F	28.05 ± 0.61	4.40
	Quality Standard 3 (QS3)	pKPC/E	24.32 ± 0.53	5.40
	Quality Standard 4 (QS4)	pKPC/D	19.39 ± 0.28	6.40
VIM	Quality Standard 1 (QS1)	pVIM/G	35.77 ± 0.08	3.19
	Quality Standard 2 (QS2)	pVIM/F	32.47 ± 0.15	4.19
	Quality Standard 3 (QS3)	pVIM/E	28.79 ± 0.02	5.19
	Quality Standard 4 (QS4)	pVIM/D	25.92 ± 0.09	6.19
NDM	Quality Standard 1 (QS1)	pNDM/G	33.75 ± 0.28	3.16
	Quality Standard 2 (QS2)	pNDM/F	30.00 ± 0.03	4.16
	Quality Standard 3 (QS3)	pNDM/E	26.14 ± 0.01	5.16
	Quality Standard 4 (QS4)	pNDM/D	23.09 ± 0.03	6.16
OXA-48	Quality Standard 1 (QS1)	pOXA-48/G	33.41 ± 0.06	3.28
	Quality Standard 2 (QS2)	pOXA-48/F	29.49 ± 0.29	4.28
	Quality Standard 3 (QS3)	pOXA-48/E	25.53 ± 0.04	5.28
	Quality Standard 4 (QS4)	pOXA-48/D	22.53 ± 0.11	6.28
IMP	Quality Standard 1 (QS1)	pIMP/F	32.36 ± 0.22	3.91
	Quality Standard 2 (QS2)	pIMP/E	28.56 ± 0.19	4.91
	Quality Standard 3 (QS3)	pIMP/D	25.08 ± 0.00	5.91
	Quality Standard 4 (QS4)	pIMP/C	21.39 ± 0.11	6.91

3.4 Discussion

Digital PCR (dPCR), particularly droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) enables the absolute quantification of nucleic acids without the need for a calibration curve. It can be used to quantify pathogens and has demonstrated reproducible and accurate performance in diagnostic applications. However, the initial setup cost is high, and its operation requires highly trained personnel (Kojabad et al., 2021).

Several studies have highlighted the use of ddPCR in detecting and quantifying CPE. For instance, Carelli et al., 2022 investigated the feasibility of using ddPCR to detect carbapenemase-resistant genes in farm animals and within the food chain. The findings suggest that ddPCR can serve as a viable alternative to traditional detection methods. Additionally, Miglietta et al., 2021 demonstrated that combining ddPCR with machine learning algorithms can significantly improve the accuracy of CPE detection in clinical samples. This method has also been employed for the rapid detection of infections caused by CPE. Wu et al., 2024 supports this with their report showing the ddPCR is a sensitive and rapid diagnostic tool for pathogen detection in suspected septic patients and was able to outperform standard blood culture methods.

This project employed qPCR as the primary method of nucleic acid quantification with a standard curve being required to determine viral load concentrations in the test samples. To ensure accuracy and consistency, the standard curve was established with use of internally developed quality standards. The concentration of the stock material used to make the quality standards was determined using ddPCR.

To assign dc/ml values to the CPE target specific plasmids, ddPCR methodology was employed using the Bio-Rad ddPCR platform. Prior to testing plasmid materials with ddPCR, the full plasmid dilution series was evaluated with the target specific PCR assay to ensure that the selected points were appropriate. This preliminary step ensured that only dilutions within the linear range of the assay were subject to ddPCR, thereby improving the accuracy of the assigned concentrations. The linearity of the plasmid dilution series was also confirmed, results presented in Chapter 2, refer to Figure 11.

Characterisation of the plasmid materials was a prerequisite for their use as reference standards in qPCR assays. To ensure comprehensive coverage, it was essential that the selected QS points spanned the expected concentration range of clinically

relevant materials. To achieve this full plasmid dilution series were assessed in parallel with biological sample materials to confirm the QS points selected adequately covered the dynamic range of detection. Alignment between the reference materials and biological targets is critical for ensuring the validity of the quantification across diverse sample types.

Following the successful quantification of the target plasmid dilution series, four points of the plasmid dilution series were selected to function as Quality Standard (QS) controls for use in subsequent qPCR assessments. Incorporating the QS points into each qPCR run, enables the generation of standard curves which facilitate the quantification of test samples. The QS points selected for each target demonstrate coverage of the Ct and Log₁₀ dc/ml ranges observed by the PC feasibility sample, results outlined in Table 29 of Chapter 4. A summary of the suitability of the QS points for each target is denoted below:

KPC target: QS Ct range was from 19.39-31.51 and Log₁₀ dc/ml range of 3.40-6.40. This encompasses the PC feasibility batch values (Ct:24.30, Log₁₀ dc/ml:5.10).

VIM Target: QS Ct range was from 25.92-35.77 and Log₁₀ dc/ml range of 3.19-6.19 This encompasses the PC feasibility batch values (Ct:29.16, Log₁₀ dc/ml:5.16).

NDM Target: QS Ct range was from 23.09-33.75 and Log₁₀ dc/ml range of 3.16-6.16 This encompasses the PC feasibility batch values (Ct:28.05, Log₁₀ dc/ml:4.71).

OXA-48 Target: QS Ct range was from 22.53-33.41 and Log₁₀ dc/ml range of 3.28-6.28 This encompasses the PC feasibility batch values (Ct:27.33, Log₁₀ dc/ml:4.89).

IMP Target: QS Ct range was from 21.39-32.26 and Log₁₀ dc/ml range of 3.91-6.91 This encompasses the PC feasibility batch values qualitatively (Ct:31.28) however the QS selection does not encompass the PC feasibility sample result (Log₁₀ dc/ml:3.70) therefore the QS range for the IMP assay needs to be broadened.

In summary the QS points selected for KPC, VIM, NDM and OXA-48 assays are able to cover the Ct and Log₁₀ range of the PC feasibility sample. IMP QS range needs to be broadened. However, the selected QS points do not extend to the clinically relevant ranges observed in the biological EQA samples. Additional work is required to ensure the QS range is broadened to encompass the concentration found in clinically relevant samples so that accurate quantification of these concentrations can be determined.

Chapter 4

Control Development

4.0 Control Development

4.1 Introduction

UKHSA 2022 emphasises the requirement that to complement culture-based methods of CPE testing, clinical diagnostic laboratories should introduce molecular or immunochromatographic assays for the detection of CPE (namely KPC, VIM, NDM and OXA-48-like). The use of molecular techniques particularly those based on PCR can be employed to rapidly detect CPE.

The need for fast, cost-effective diagnostic methods allows for early detection of outbreaks and intervention of treatment to guide patient care, as well as facilitating the surveillance of resistant genes. Moloney et al., 2019 suggests that the introduction of PCR based methodologies in replacement of culture-based methods within the UK NHS could be economically beneficial due to the fast turnaround time of results leading to less strain on resources taken in isolating high-risk patients.

To enhance quality control (QC) protocols, it is essential that highly characterised control materials are available. Giannoli et al., 2025 underscores the essential role internal quality control (IQC) plays in ensuring laboratories fulfil regulatory requirements in the accreditation process. The document outlines the methods used to ensure quality of clinical laboratory performance. IQC materials must demonstrate similar concentration levels and matrix characteristics that are comparable to patient samples, material must also be assessed in the same manner as patient samples to allow accurate results, these materials are used to highlight any differences in detection performance, deviations from a defined state to ensure confidence in the methodologies used to evaluate clinical samples. This document shows that the use of positive control reference materials are vital for any standard molecular test, the accuracy of data gathered depends on the assays' ability to detect a specific analyte. The control material can be of significant benefit to laboratories in assessing performance of their molecular technologies. True amplification of positive control material contributes significantly to the validation of experimental results. Positive controls are intended to contain a specific analyte and measure the performance of testing methodologies. Without a positive control it is difficult to confirm the validity of a negative result which could occur due the absence of the analyte or due to failure at some step of the testing process. It is essential that testing for CPE is accurate and can be relied upon as false negative results will influence patient care, which could

not only be detrimental to the health of a patient but could also lead to widespread outbreaks. The use of full process positive controls can act as a benchmark for data and mitigate the risk of false positives.

Therefore, in this chapter considerations were taken to ensure that control material designed was compatible with molecular technologies that are widely used in the detection of carbapenem resistant genes KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP, and able to function as a full process run control. The control material should be designed to be compatible for use with both commercial and in-house assays and consisting of clinically relevant quantities of the target nucleic acids.

First, the biological materials (EQA samples) were assessed to define their concentrations, this was done to allow the positive control material being designed to be compatible for use in IQC processes. An initial assessment of the individual biological samples intended for inclusion in the control was conducted. The review of EQA programmes in Chapter 2 highlighted suitable samples within the EQAs, that have a determined clinical relevance i.e. samples that have been detected accurately by above 93% of participating laboratories. The compatibility of the biological materials and the developed in-house assays was proven to be viable in Chapter 2.

Alternative stock materials were considered for use for inclusion in the development of the positive control material. Due to limitations in the availability of biological stock materials Whole Gene synthetic constructs were considered for use in the development of the control.

It is intended that the positive control material developed can be used as a run control in the detection of CPE as well as for the verification and validation of workflows. The focus of the project was on the five most prevalent carbapenem resistant genes requires control material to be developed for each of these enzymes. Feasibility assessment was carried out in this chapter to explore the compatibility of a multiplex positive control; control materials containing analytes for each of the five selected CPE genes. The production of a multiplex control is advantageous as it is a cost reduction for laboratories, with only one positive control sample required for the verification and validation of multiple molecular assays that detect CPE. The control could also be used routinely for the assessment of multiplex assays that detect two or more target genes in the same reaction.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Assessment of Biological Materials

Feasibility assessment aimed to determine the viability of the selected biological stock materials for inclusion in the PC sample formulation was conducted. Given the limited volume of biological material available, sample dilutions of the biological samples were prepared, establishing if the target gene sequences remained detectable at lower concentrations.

Ten-fold serial dilutions (logarithmic dilution) of biological (EQA) materials were prepared for each of the CPE genes. This was prepared to allow enough sample material to be available for testing as the biological sample material levels were limited. Individual sample dilutions of biological materials were conducted for each of the CPE genes. Table 22 displays the dilution plan for KPC assay biological sample, this was similarly performed for VIM and IMP targets. Duplex biological material containing NDM and OXA-48 target analytes was selected for use and therefore this material was assessed for both target assays.

One of the most essential parameters to be set out in the assay development process is to determine the minimum level at which an analyte can be accurately detected and quantified. The sample dilution series, in addition to the plasmid material assessed in Chapter 2 assists in determining the sensitivity of the developed assays and defining the dynamic range of the assays as well as defining the assay limit of detection (LoD) and the limit of quantification (LoQ). The LoD is the lowest amount of a target or analyte that the assay can detect 95% of the time and the LoQ is the lowest concentration that can be accurately detected quantitatively and with precision 95% of the time (Forootan et al., 2017). An additional half-logarithmic dilution series was prepared, Table 23, this expanded the concentration determined in the first Log-dilution to confirm final assay LoD and LoQ.

Sample dilutions were prepared in transport medium (TM), a standard media matrix. This was done to mimic typical clinical sample specimens. To preserve sample specimens during transport to laboratory for testing, a suitable transport media is required to maintain the integrity of the clinical sample gathered, preserving the viability of microorganism prior to testing (Erkmen, 2021).

Table 22. KPC Biological Stock material 10-Fold Serial Dilution Plan

Table comprises of Log₁₀ increments in a 9-point dilution series. All concentrations are in digital copies (dc/ml)

Step	Start Concentration (dc/mL)	Stock Volume (mL)	Diluent Volume (TM) (mL)	Total (ml)	Ratio	New Concentration (dc/mL)	Use in Next Step (ml)	Batch Code
1	1.51E+08	0.25	2.25	2.5	0.1	1.51E+07	1	KPC2406014A
2	1.51E+07	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+06	1	KPC2406014B
3	1.51E+06	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+05	1	KPC2406014C
4	1.51E+05	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+04	1	KPC2406014D
5	1.51E+04	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+03	1	KPC2406014E
6	1.51E+03	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+02	1	KPC2406014F
7	1.51E+02	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+01	1	KPC2406014G
8	1.51E+01	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E+00	1	KPC2406014H
9	1.51E+00	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E-00	1	KPC2406014I
10	1.51E-00	1	9	10	0.1	1.51E-01	0	KPC2406014J

Table 23. KPC Biological Stock Material Additional Half-Log Serial Dilution Plan

Table comprises of Half-Log₁₀ increments in a 3-point dilution series. All concentrations are in digital copies (dc/ml)

Step	Start Concentration (dc/mL)	Stock Volume (mL)	Diluent Volume (TM) (mL)	Total (ml)	Ratio	New Concentration (dc/mL)	Use in Next Step (ml)	Batch Code
1	1.51E+04	0.6	1.296	1.896	0.32	4.78E+03	0.6	KPC2504050A
2	4.78E+03	0.6	1.296	1.896	0.32	1.51E+03	0.6	KPC2504050B
3	1.51E+03	0.6	1.296	1.896	0.32	4.79E+02	0.0	KPC2504050C

4.2.2 Feasibility of Multiplex Control

The development of a multiplex positive control was initiated by performing feasibility testing to provide proof of concept for a multiplex CPE control.

Equal volumes of each target assay clinical material were combined to generate the multiplex pool sample. For each target, a point of the 10-fold sample dilution series was selected and pooled into the multiplex positive control sample. Table 24 below shows the components the CPE PC Sample made. Two batches of the feasibility positive control were prepared in the same way (Batch 1 and Batch 2).

Table 24. CPE PC Sample Components

Sample Reference	Start concentration Arbitrary Units (AU/mL)	Stock Volume (mL)	New Concentration Arbitrary Units (AU/mL)	Batch Code
IMP Sample Dilution Point D	1.00E+05	1.1	2.50E+04	CPE PC Sample
KPC Sample Dilution Point B	1.00E+05	1.1	2.50E+04	
NDM_OXA Sample Dilution Point B	1.00E+05	1.1	2.50E+04	
VIM Sample Dilution Point B	1.00E+05	1.1	2.50E+04	
IMP Sample Dilution Point D	1.00E+05	1.1	2.50E+04	

Table 25. CPE PC Dilution Sample Components

Serial dilution of the CPE PC Sample was performed: Transport medium was used as used as the diluent

Step	Start Conc (AU/mL)	Stock Volume (mL)	Diluent Volume (TM) (mL)	Total (ml)	Ratio	New Conc (AU/mL)	Use in Next Step (ml)	Batch Code
1	2.50E+04	0.5	4.5	5	0.1	2.50E+03	0.5	CPE PC Sample (1in10)
2	2.50E+03	0.5	4.5	5	0.1	2.50E+02	0	CPE PC Sample (1in100)

4.2.3 Whole Gene Plasmid Constructs consideration

Whole Gene (WG) plasmid constructs were developed, for each of the target genes of interest, gene bank accession numbers denoted by Table 5 were accessed with the whole gene sequenced used to design plasmid constructs. As opposed to the design of the plasmid materials that have been developed for use as QS materials where a specific region of the gene sequence was selected, for this process the entire coding sequence of the analyte was selected. The inclusion of the entire gene sequence allows for the detection of the target of interest and so can be suitable for use as a positive control material.

Section 2.2.6 'Construction of Plasmid Standards' discussed the design, development of plasmid standards for use in qPCR assessment, the WG plasmid constructs were designed in the same manner. Individual WG plasmid constructs consisting of the entire gene sequence was designed for each CPE target of interest. The plasmid materials were manufactured externally by Eurofins genomics; on arrival the lyophilised pellet was reconstituted in 1x TE Buffer and serial dilutions were prepared. Table 26 denotes the dilution plan for the KPC whole gene plasmid construct designed.

Table 26. KPC Whole Gene Plasmid Constructs 10-Fold Serial Dilution Plan

Table comprises of Log₁₀ increments in a 9-point dilution series. All concentrations are in arbitrary units (AU/ml)

Step	Start Conc (AU/ml)	Stock Volume (ml)	Diluent Volume (1xTE Buffer) (ml)	Total (ml)	Ratio	New Conc (AU/ml)	Use in Next Step (ml)	Batch Code
1	1.00E+09	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+08	0.05	pWG/KPC/A
2	1.00E+08	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+07	0.05	pWG/KPC/B
3	1.00E+07	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+06	0.05	pWG/KPC/C
4	1.00E+06	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+05	0.05	pWG/KPC/D
5	1.00E+05	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+04	0.05	pWG/KPC/E
6	1.00E+04	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+03	0.05	pWG/KPC/F
7	1.00E+03	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+02	0.05	pWG/KPC/G
8	1.00E+02	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+01	0.05	pWG/KPC/H
9	1.00E+01	0.05	0.45	0.5	0.1	1.00E+00	0	pWG/KPC/I

The five CPE quantitative assays developed in Chapter 2 were used to evaluate the biological sample material dilutions, the positive control samples and the WG plasmid constructs. Additionally, Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay was utilised to evaluate the performance of the multiplex control formulation for detecting CPE genes of interest.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Assessment of Biological Materials

To determine the performance of each of the qPCR assays developed, the LoD and LoQ were established. Biological samples materials were serially diluted in 1 log increments as shown by Table 22 above. Figure 16 below shows the linearity of each

sample dilution for each assay. The LoD and LoQ results were supported by an additional sample dilution whereby biological sample material were further diluted in half log increments to confirm results and establish assay LoD and LoQ. Figure 17 below depicts these results. Table 27 denotes the established LoD and LoQ result for each assay. Results from the combined two series were used to conclude the LoD and LoQ, the first dilution series was used to assess the standing limits of the assay, and the second dilution series defined the exact assay limitations.

Table 27. Determined LoD and LoQ Results for CPE In-House Assays

Number of replicates amplified was two and is noted as (N=2)

Assay	LoD Observed (Ct Value)	LoQ Observed (Log₁₀ dc/ml Value)
KPC	35.83 ± 0.07	2.38 ± 0.02
VIM	38.40 ± 0.83	2.14 ± 0.25
NDM	39.29 ± 0.76	1.49 ± 0.20
OXA-48	38.00 ± 0.56	1.95 ± 0.16
IMP	41.40 ± 0.27	1.40 ± 0.07

(A) KPC

(B) VIM

(C) NDM

(D) OXA-48

(E) IMP

Figure 16. 10-fold Log Dilution Linearity-Biological Sample Dilution Series

Panels 16A-16E show standard curves for KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP assays, demonstrating linear dilution series observed.

(A) KPC

(B) VIM

(C) NDM

(D) OXA-48

(E) IMP

Figure 17. Half-Log Dilution Linearity-Biological Sample Dilution Series

Panels 17A-17E show standard curves for KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP assays, demonstrating linear dilution series observed

4.3.2 Feasibility of Multiplex Control

The aim of the qPCR assessment of the PC multiplex batches, as shown in Table 28 and Table 29, was to evaluate the performance and consistency of the PC multiplex formulation. Each test run included the PC multiplex sample alongside the PC multiplex sample dilutions (1in10, 1in100), to assess reproducibility and sensitivity of the control. Table 28 and 29 also compare the PC multiplex sample and the biological sample dilution points used as stock materials, allowing for validation of the controls ability to reflect biological samples.

Table 28. Positive control IHA feasibility results, batch 1

Number of replicates amplified was two and is noted as (N=2)

Target Name	Sample Reference	Mean Ct Value	Log ₁₀ dc/ml
KPC	KPC Sample Dilution Point B	25.34 ± 0.14	5.29 ± 0.03
	CPE PC Sample	25.57 ± 0.29	5.23 ± 0.07
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	29.82 ± 0.32	4.15 ± 0.08
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	33.15 ± 0.17	3.30 ± 0.04
VIM	VIM Sample Dilution Point B	24.33 ± 0.21	5.99 ± 0.06
	CPE PC Sample	26.21 ± 0.12	5.49 ± 0.03
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	31.26 ± 0.03	4.10 ± 0.01
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	35.67 ± 0.18	2.88 ± 0.05
NDM	NDM_OXA Sample Dilution Point B	26.23 ± 0.27	6.29 ± 0.07
	CPE PC Sample	26.47 ± 0.14	6.22 ± 0.04
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	31.16 ± 0.01	4.97 ± 0.00
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	33.82 ± 0.06	4.25 ± 0.02
OXA-48	NDM_OXA Sample Dilution Point B	25.99 ± 0.23	5.37 ± 0.07
	CPE PC Sample	26.09 ± 0.13	5.34 ± 0.04
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	30.93 ± 0.08	3.96 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	34.28 ± 0.05	3.01 ± 0.01

Table 29. Positive control IHA feasibility results, batch 2*Number of replicates amplified was two and is noted as (N=2(*N=1))*

Target Name	Sample Reference	Mean Ct Value	Log₁₀ dc/ml
KPC	KPC Biological Material (EQA Sample)	15.70 ± 1.11	8.10 ± 0.39
	CPE PC Sample	24.30 ± 0.27	5.10 ± 0.09
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	28.02 ± 2.51	3.80 ± 0.88
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	32.34 ± 0.63	2.29 ± 0.22
VIM	VIM Biological Material (EQA Sample)	19.46 ± 0.03	8.08 ± 0.01
	CPE PC Sample	29.16 ± 0.06	5.16 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	32.56 ± 0.06	4.14 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	36.18*	3.05*
NDM	NDM_OXA Biological Material (EQA Sample)	18.93 ± 0.06	7.25 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample	28.05 ± 0.29	4.71 ± 0.08
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	31.33 ± 0.05	3.79 ± 0.01
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	34.89 ± 0.026	2.80 ± 0.07
OXA-48	NDM_OXA Biological Material (EQA Sample)	17.63 ± 0.08	7.54 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample	27.33 ± 0.06	4.89 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	30.21 ± 0.10	4.10 ± 0.03
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	34.11 ± 0.08	3.04 ± 0.02
IMP	IMP Biological Material (EQA Sample)	No Amplification	No Amplification
	CPE PC Sample	31.28 ± 0.13	3.70 ± 0.04
	CPE PC Sample (1in10)	35.21 ± 0.05	2.50 ± 0.02
	CPE PC Sample (1in100)	38.63 ± 0.71	1.45 ± 0.22

Data graphs depicted by Figure 18 and 19 below have been prepared for the qPCR results. The fluorescence has been plotted against the Log₁₀ dc/ml result for each assay.

Figure 18. Linearity of Multiplex Positive Control (Batch 1): Feasibility Assessment of Individual CPE Assays (KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48)

Testing demonstrated linearity for the multiplex positive control across four of the CPE assays. Although the control contains multiple targets, results were obtained separately for each assay, confirming consistent amplification and reliable performance for each target.

Figure 19. Linearity of Multiplex Positive Control (Batch 2): Feasibility Assessment of Individual CPE Assays (KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP)

Testing demonstrated linearity for the multiplex positive control across five of the CPE assays. Although the control contains multiple targets, results were obtained separately for each assay, confirming consistent amplification and reliable performance for each target.

Table 30 below shows the Cepheid GeneXpert results gathered. Only one reaction is performed for each cartridge, therefore a limited number of tests were conducted using this platform. KPC and IMP biological sample dilution points were assessed as well as the CPE PC material.

Table 30. Biological Material Assessment on Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R Assay
Each sample assessed in one Cepheid reaction(N=1)

Sample Reference	Ct Value	Analyte Detected
KPC Sample Dilution point C	26.0	KPC
KPC Sample Dilution point D	29.8	KPC
IMP Sample Dilution point A	18.8	IMP
CPE PC Sample	24.1	KPC
	22.3	VIM
	22.6	NDM
	22.1	OXA-48
	25.4	IMP
CPE PC Sample(1in10) Dilution	29.4	KPC
	27.1	VIM
	27.7	NDM
	26.8	OXA-48
	30.5	IMP

4.3.3 Whole Gene Plasmid Constructs Consideration

Initial qPCR testing was conducted to assess the performance of the whole gene plasmid constructs when used directly as DNA template in qPCR setup, without prior extraction. The data gathered shows that the WG constructs had linear amplification as illustrated by Figure 20 . Additionally, Table 31 denotes Mean Ct and Mean Log₁₀ dc/ml values that are comparative to biological sample materials, suggesting that these WG constructs effectively mimic clinical samples and so could be used as suitable alternatives to biological materials.

(A) KPC

(B) VIM

(C) NDM

(D) OXA-48

(E) IMP

Figure 20. Plasmid Whole Gene Sequence qPCR Results

Panels 20A-20E show standard curves for KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP assays, demonstrating linear dilution series observed

Table 31. Biological Material and WG Plasmid Dilution IHA Results*Number of replicates amplified was two and is noted as (N=2(*N=1))*

Target	Sample Reference	Mean Ct Value	Mean Log ₁₀ dc/ml
KPC	KPC Biological Material (EQA Sample)	15.70 ± 1.11	8.10 ± 0.39
	pWG/KPC/B	14.34 ± 0.49	8.57 ± 0.17
	pWG/KPC/C	17.01 ± 0.43	7.64 ± 0.15
VIM	VIM Biological Material (EQA Sample)	19.46 ± 0.03	8.08 ± 0.01
	pWG/VIM/B	18.93 ± 0.13	8.24 ± 0.04
	pWG/VIM/C	23.09 ± 0.03	6.99 ± 0.01
NDM	NDM_OXA-48 Biological Material (EQA Sample)	18.93 ± 0.06	7.25 ± 0.02
	pWG/NDM/B	16.05 ± 0.17	8.06 ± 0.05
	pWG/NDM/C	20.13 ± 0.04	6.92 ± 0.01
OXA-48	NDM_OXA-48 Biological Material (EQA Sample)	17.63 ± 0.08	7.54 ± 0.02
	*pWG/OXA-48/B	18.93 ± 0.06	7.25 ± 0.02
	pWG/OXA-48/C	22.47 ± 0.03	6.22 ± 0.01
IMP	IMP Biological Dilution Point A	30.47 ± 0.02	4.41 ± 0.01
	pWG/IMP/E	27.91 ± 0.67	4.73 ± 0.21
	pWG/IMP/F	31.44 ± 0.67	3.65 ± 0.21

IMP Biological Dilution Point Used as reference only as sample was not assed on the same qPCR plate as WG plasmids so direct comparison cannot be made.

4.4 Discussion

This chapter explored the feasibility of the development of a multiplex control containing the five most prevalent CPE genes. The integration of multiple analytes into a single multiplex control enables simultaneous monitoring of several targets, reducing the need for multiple individual control materials. This approach allows for greater flexibility, as a variety of analytes can be included to accommodate different testing requirements and assay platforms. In standard molecular diagnostic workflows, a positive control is typically included once per run to verify assay performance (Ezzelle et al., 2008). Therefore, the implementation of a multiplex control offers both cost-effectiveness and time efficiency by consolidating multiple targets into a single control material. This not only streamlines laboratory workflows but also supports consistent quality assurance across diverse molecular testing platforms.

Multiple studies have demonstrated the successful application of multiplex positive controls in molecular diagnostics. For example, Jolinda de Korne-Elenbaas et al. (2024) outlined the design and validation of multiplex digital PCR assays and advocated for the use of positive control materials that include all target sequences being evaluated. The study also recommended pooling controls of similar concentrations to improve assay efficiency and consistency. Similarly, Osman et al. (2013) combined three different viral targets into a single positive control reaction. Their multiplex RT-qPCR assays showed effective amplification of all three viruses, confirming the feasibility of using mixed control templates. Earlier work by Charrel, Scola, and Didier Raoult (2004) also demonstrated the successful use of dual plasmid constructs as positive control material, supporting the concept of combining multiple targets into a single control. In another example, Standish et al. (2018) developed a multiplex control containing three target genes, further validating the practicality of this approach for routine diagnostic use. These studies collectively support the strategy employed in this project, where multiple carbapenemase resistance genes were combined into a single multiplex control. The literature reinforces the value of multiplex controls in improving assay reliability, reducing reagent use, and streamlining workflow validation.

Initial assessment of the individual biological samples intended for inclusion in the control was conducted. Sample dilutions were prepared from selected starting materials and the five CPE quantitative assays developed evaluated the performance of the material. It is essential to establish assay limitations to understand the concentration at which analytical measurement data is reliable and accurate.

Table 27 represents the determined LoD and LoQ for each target. However, it is important to note that each sample was only assessed in duplicate only, which limits the robustness of the results. Additional testing with increased replicate numbers will confirm these preliminary results ensuring reliability and reproducibility of the assay performance.

Figure 16 depicts Assay Sample 10-fold Log dilution linearity results and Figure 17 depicts Assay Sample Half-Log dilution linearity results. Both Figures show that the biological stock dilutions are linear as the R^2 value equals 1.

Table 28 represents the multiplex control batch 1 IHA feasibility results. qPCR assay performance was assessed for the biological start sample dilution point used for the formulation of the control, the multiplex control as well as a 1in10 and 1in100 dilution of the multiplex control. Results show that the PC feasibility multiplex sample has similar performance to that of the biological sample dilution point used as stock material for the PC. This is indicative that pooling the analyte samples together into a multiplex control has minor impact on detection results, this supports the use of the multiplex control.

As the multiplex is cheaper and more convenient than individual positive controls and performs as well as the simplex controls the multiplex format is preferred for the CPE PC control.

Table 29 shows performance of batch 2 PC samples as well as results for the biological material (EQA sample).

Figures 18 and 19 depict a linear relationship between the concentration of each target and the Ct value obtained for all CPE Assay targets. The data shows control prepared is detectable for all targets. However, the multiplex control has been formulated using dilutions of the selected EQA biological samples. Performance at a clinically relevant level still needs assessed.

Table 30 denotes the performance of CPE biological stock materials with use of Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay. CPE PC sample formulation was assessed and showed to be able to detect all five CPE target genes well, the 1in10 dilution of the PC also showed detection for the five CPE targets. KPC and IMP diluted biological samples were also assessed with this methodology, results show that for KPC Sample Dilution points C and D, KPC target was detected only. IMP Sample Dilution point A only detected IMP analyte. Detection of the CPE multiplex positive control was shown across both the laboratory developed IHA and the commercially available Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay. Additional results gathered for IMP target has been discussed in Chapter 2, results gathered during assay development optimisation test runs, Table 13 and Figure 10 show IHA results of CPE PC batch 1 1in100 sample results as well as IMP biological dilution point D.

The development of the control material described in this project is intended to be detected across different users and workflows, enabling the monitoring of performance, detection of assay drift and management of performance. Thus, allowing for reliable results to be gathered and supporting to control the spread and outbreak of resistance CPE genes.

The challenge of obtaining rare or emerging pathogens for use as positive control material has led to synthetic materials being incorporated into the development of PCs. One study conducted in 2013 by Caasi et al., explored the use of artificial positive controls (APCs), whereby PCR testing was conducted to compare the performance of APCs with standard reference positive control (virus infected plant tissue). The APC designed optimally had a 100% amplification rate compared to a 92% amplification rate for the reference PC. A study carried out by Krüttgen et al., 2011 showed successful use of a chemically synthetic NDM gene as use as a PC material to setup and optimize their novel PCR assays.

qPCR evaluation established the linearity of the Whole Gene (WG) plasmid dilution series. Synthetic plasmid construct was designed and developed to act as an alternative to the biological materials. Figure 20 depicts the WG plasmid dilutions results which shows that each target there is a linear relationship between the concentration and Ct value.

The WG Plasmid dilution series were tested alongside clinically relevant biological samples to determine which dilution points had comparable Ct values to that of the

clinical samples, see Table 31. The positive control material should be in line with the biological materials.

KPC clinically relevant biological material (EQA sample) results show a mean Ct value of 15.70 ± 1.11 and a Log₁₀ dc/ml value of 8.10 ± 0.39 . This result sits in between results observed for pWG/KPC/B and pWG/KPC/C as shown by Table 31. The data shows that between point B and C of the WG plasmid dilution series is the level at which results are in line with clinically relevant sample performance, thus clinically relevant WG plasmid points have been identified for development of positive control material with this material. VIM, NDM and OXA-48 biological material (EQA sample) result also sits between WG plasmid dilution points B and C.

IMP biological sample did not amplify for the IMP target, Internal control was positive with a Ct result of 31.27 ± 0.10 , further optimisation of the IMP assay is required to ensure that clinically relevant levels of IMP can be detected. Biological material dilution point A, which is a half-log dilution of the starting biological material, appears to have similar amplification to between points E and F of the WG plasmid dilution, the result show on Table 31 however is used only as a reference as sample was not assed on the same qPCR plate as WG plasmids so direct comparison cannot be made.

Further testing required to assess the feasibility of using these synthetic constructs as positive controls is required. Testing should be carried out to assess how the material performs through nucleic acid extraction to assess performance as a full process control and the impact this has on results.

Manufacturing the control has areas of risk that need to be considered, possible areas that could cause variation in the control include inadequate concentrations levels of biological stocks used in the development process resulting in limited detection, inadequate preparation including during the mixing and dispensing process, formulation of the dilution, stability of the control and risk of freeze thaw degradation. The proposed control is limited to assessing detection of the five most prevalent CPE resistant genes however, less common and unknown genes will not be detected. The inclusion of synthetic plasmid constructs within the control has a high contamination risk, feasibility assessment of the use of this material is required to assesses its suitability as a full process control.

Chapter 5

Final Discussion and Conclusions

5.0 Final Discussion and Conclusions

5.1 Overview of Project Aims

This project aimed to address the diagnostic challenges associated with the detection of Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (CPE) by developing a molecular reference control. The material was intended to function as a full process control compatible with both the Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay and In-house qPCR assays. With the purpose of supporting the validation, verification and quality assurance of CPE detection platforms.

5.2 Selection of Clinically Relevant Carbapenemase Resistant Genes Using EQA and Literature

The first objective focused on ensuring that the positive control material developed in this project would be compatible across different molecular diagnostic platforms. To achieve this, biological materials were selected based on their demonstrated performance in External Quality Assessment (EQA) schemes. EQA programmes are widely considered as essential tools for monitoring and evaluation laboratory performance (Laudus et al., 2022). Materials with detection rates above 93% across participating laboratories were considered. Data from Table 10, illustrates that each selected sample achieved detection rates above 94% confirming their applicability and clinical relevance.

This approach is in line with recommended laboratory practices for diagnostic testing whereby the use of specific control material are essential. Controls should be fit for purpose and show consistent and measurable responses that reflect real world scenarios. Giannoli et al., 2021 highlights the importance of using clinically relevant controls is vital in ensuring accuracy, reproducibility and reliability of molecular diagnostics that is reflective of patient samples.

Leveraging samples validated via EQA participation supports that the control materials developed in this project are representative of commonly encountered CPE strains and meet robust and reproducibility criteria required for use in molecular diagnostics. This ensured that the control materials were clinically relevant, representative of commonly encountered CPE strains and suitable for use in diverse laboratory settings.

5.3 Development and Evaluation of In-House Assays

The second objective involved the design and development of in-house qPCR assays to target the five predominant carbapenemase genes: KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48, and IMP. These genes collectively known as the 'big five' represent the most clinically significant carbapenemases globally, they account for over 97% of CPE in England (Jenkins et al., 2024). A study conducted by Haji, Aka and Ali 2021 highlighted the prevalence of the 'big five' carbapenemase genes within clinical samples. The findings revealed that 30.9% of isolates assessed exhibited carbapenem resistance, with 59% being identified as carbapenemase producers. Among these NDM was the most frequently detected gene, accounting for 83% of cases, OXA-48 was present in 75% of isolates, VIM genes were detected in 49% of cases, IMP accounted for 43% and KPC 7%. These results indicate the widespread distribution of carbapenem resistant genes and reinforces the importance of inclusion of the 'big five' genes in molecular diagnostic strategies.

The performance of the assays were evaluated using qPCR, the EQA data reviewed as represented by Table 15 further supports the inclusion of the five resistance genes in the assay development process. Furthermore, the continued development of assays targeting these genes is supported by innovations in molecular biology. Reinicke et al., 2025 introduced the CarbaScan LyoBead qPCR assay, which demonstrated 100% sensitivity and specificity when detecting these genes. This data confirmed the relevance of inclusion of the five CPE resistance genes into molecular controls.

5.4 Multiplex Control Design

The final objective focused on the development and evaluation of a multiplex CPE positive control designed for compatibility across both the IHAs and Cepheid GeneXpert platform. As detailed in Chapter 4, the control was successfully detected across all five resistance genes (KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP) using both platforms.

The development of robust and reliable control materials is essential in molecular diagnostic testing. Multiplex controls offer a significant advantage by allowing simultaneous detection of multiple targets within a single reaction. The development and introduction of multiplex assays supports the use of such controls, Yoshioka et al., 2021 developed a multiplex real-time PCR assay and demonstrates the clinical utility

of multiplex PCR assays and reinforces the need for robust controls. The research carried out highlights the importance of accurate and cost-effective methodologies and reagents, that could aid early detection of CPE.

This project assessed both biological materials and synthetic control constructs with preliminary results indicating reliable amplification and comparable performance to that of biological stock materials. However, a noted limitation of the current control is that the concentrations of the biological materials are not yet aligned with clinically relevant levels. Additional optimisation and validation is required to ensure that the control is able to reliably detect Carbapenemase at concentrations reflective of real-world clinical samples.

The importance of standardized and clinically relevant controls is highlighted by Jing et al., 2018, this review explores the urgent requirement of appropriate reference materials. This material can be used to harmonize and standardize results across laboratories.

5.5 Public Health Implications and Diagnostic Relevance

Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE) are a significant and escalating global public health threat (CDC, 2023). This fact is further supported by the review conducted by Gualtiero Alvisi et al., 2025, which indicates the severe public health implications related to CPE and illustrates the risk posed due to their resistance mechanisms which can enable their rapid spread in hospital settings. These genes can be transmitted to other bacteria species resulting in increased financial strain on healthcare providers ineffective treatment and raised mortality rates. The implementation of stringent infection control measures and suitable detection methods is essential in clinical environments.

Accurate and timely CPE detection is essential for controlling outbreaks and mitigating the spread of resistant genes. According to the WHO 2024 Bacterial Priority Pathogens List (WHO, 2024) CRE are classified within the highest critical group. Carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is identified as the most immediate threat, emphasising the ongoing risk to public health and the urgency for advanced CRE management strategies. Infections associated with CRE can lead to prolonged hospitalization and complex outbreak scenarios. Therefore, the WHO List serves as a

key tool for informing public health policies, prioritising research and allocation of funds to combat antimicrobial resistance on a global scale.

The rapid and accurate detection of CPE is crucial for the timely administration of antimicrobial therapy; the prevention of hospital acquired transmission and the reduction of morbidity and mortality rates. The development and implementation of robust clinically relevant molecular reference controls is essential to ensure the accurate and reliable detection of CPE in diagnostic laboratories. Molecular diagnostic tests have been increasingly favoured to allow rapid turnaround of results compared to culture methods. As highlighted by Ambretti et al. (2019) the challenges of screening for CRE within a healthcare setting underscores the requirements for active surveillance, with molecular diagnostics playing a significant role.

The integration of reliable positive controls into these workflows safeguards the integrity of rapid molecular testing and promotes consistency and standardisation across different laboratories which is particularly important in outbreak situations and for periods of heightened screening. WHO 2024 and UKHSA 2022 have both highlighted the requirements for advancements in detection measure for CPE.

Despite advancements in CPE detection strategies, current methodologies have limitations. PCR based assays commonly used are inherently limited to the specific gene targets they are designed to amplify. Increased spread and emergency of rare and new carbapenemase variants means that these molecular assays may fail to detect variants not included in their design. In such cases, culture-based methods may offer a complementary advantage, enabling the identification of less common or novel carbapenemase genes that fall outside the scope of standard PCR assays. Undetected resistance gene can lead to false negative results resulting in infected patients being incorrectly categorised, treatment delays and infection control failures which can increase the risk of transmission rates (Li et al., 2024).

5.6 Limitations and Further Work

While the primary aims of the project have been achieved, several limitations have been identified:

- Assay design and positive control formulation focused exclusively on the 'big five' carbapenemases, limiting detection and validation of platforms with less common resistance genes.
- The positive control formulation requires further optimisation to ensure that concentrations reflect clinically relevant levels.
- IMP assay demonstrated suboptimal amplification efficiency at clinically relevant concentrations. Further optimisation to improve amplification efficiency is required to ensure that all five target genes in the multiplex control can be reliably detected under routine testing conditions.
- Current Quality Standards selected only align with the PC sample; further optimisation is required to ensure qPCR assays are able to accurately quantify samples at clinically relevant levels.

To address the identified limitations and enhance the clinical applicability and robustness of the developed multiplex CPE control, the following areas of future work are proposed:

The control material must be evaluated at clinically relevant concentrations, the current formulation prepared with biological sample dilutions has demonstrated strong performance on IHAs and Cepheid platform, providing proof of concept for the use of these control materials. Additional testing is required to ensure that the developed multiplex control material mimics real clinical samples.

The precision and reproducibility of the control should be evaluated through repeat testing by multiple operators. This will involve the use of a blind panel of samples tested independently by at least two additional users. Reproducibility will be assessed by comparing results across users and platforms to ensure consistency and robustness of the control material.

Homogeneity testing is also necessary to verify batch-to-batch consistency of the manufactured controls. Successful results would demonstrate uniform detection across different production lots and molecular platforms, supporting the control's reliability in routine use.

Long-term stability assessments are also essential. This will involve storing the control material under defined conditions and testing at regular intervals to assess

degradation or performance loss over time. Stability data will provide evidence for the control's shelf life.

External validation of the multiplex control should be pursued to confirm its performance across a range of laboratories and molecular workflows. This will help establish its stability and ensure that it meets the needs of diverse diagnostic settings.

Additionally, further exploration into the use of synthetic plasmid constructs is warranted. While synthetic controls are useful for evaluating PCR amplification, they do not challenge the nucleic acid extraction step of diagnostic workflows. Due to the size of the full gene sequences, a single multiplexed construct was not feasible. Instead, individual whole-gene plasmid constructs were developed for each of the five CPE resistance genes. Future work should assess the performance of these constructs and their impact on assay sensitivity and workflow integration.

Collectively, these future directions will support the refinement and broader implementation of the multiplex CPE control, contributing to improved diagnostic accuracy and antimicrobial resistance surveillance.

5.2 Final Conclusions

This project successfully fulfilled its primary objective: the development of molecular reference control material for the detection of Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriales (CPE). The control material developed demonstrated compatibility with both qPCR IHAs and the Cepheid GeneXpert Carba-R assay.

A detailed review of EQA data and the current literature led to the identification of the five most clinically significant Carbapenemase resistant genes: KPC, VIM, NDM, OXA-48 and IMP. The targets were selected due to their global prevalence ensuring the control material would be widely applicable.

The inclusion of these targets informed the design and development of the qPCR assays. The use of ddPCR enabled appropriate reference standards to be appointed for each assay, thus ensuring the biological samples assessed could be suitably quantified.

The resulting multiplex control developed here represents a valuable tool for supporting the validation and optimisation of molecular workflows for CPE detection.

The implementation of this control material can enhance the consistency and reliability of CPE detection, contributing to improved diagnostic accuracy and supporting broader efforts in antimicrobial resistance management.

The work here contributes meaningfully to the global effort to monitor and mitigate antimicrobial resistance, reinforcing the critical role of rapid and reliable diagnostics.

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